

Codebook for Human Coding of Newspaper Articles

Higher Ed Protest Event Dataset (HiPED) Project

Authors: Alex Hanna and Ellen Berrey

alex.hanna@gmail.com, ellen.berrey@utoronto.ca

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NOTE TO EXTERNAL READERS

We continually updated the *Codebook* with clarifications, further instructions, and decisions on particular events throughout the coding process. This version of the project’s *Codebook* has been modified slightly to include explanatory notes and formatting changes; however, the content is the same as the original document which research assistants referred to as they coded newspaper articles.

Footnotes that come from the original document are noted as such; all other footnotes are explanatory for external readers. Hyperlinks to internal project documents were removed, but noted.

INTRODUCTION

The intention of this research project is to **create event data on university and college (higher education) protests in Canada and the United States and university responses between 2012 and 2018**. We have a special analytic interest in anti-racism protest, but we are studying higher education protest on a wide range of issues, from fossil fuel divestment to labour protections to White supremacy. Our ultimate goal is to understand large-scale patterns in student and campus protest movements and universities’ management of protests.

To understand those patterns, we are creating the Student & Campus Protest Events Dataset. Constructing the dataset involves using computational text analysis and then sociological hand-coding of all student and campus protests reported in student newspapers. Research assistants on the team, like yourself, do the hand-coding: they identify and mark protest-related information within newspaper articles using an online interface. In each article, coders determine if the article included information about a protest event that meets our criteria for a higher education protest. If the article does, coders identify specific characteristics of the protest such as

location, duration, form, and issue. This process is aided by the Machine-learning Protest Event Data System (MPEDS), a system for generating protest event data using tools from natural language processing and statistics. Ellen Berrey oversees the work of hand-coding, Alex Hanna created and oversees MPEDS.

A thorough and nuanced training strategy for teaching RAs how to understand and apply this codebook was developed over many years and led by project manager Sara Wasim. For details, see her [*Summary of Coding Training Strategy*](#).¹

How To Use This Codebook

This codebook provides criteria to help you make decisions as you code student newspaper articles on protest events. **Understanding the codebook is essential to coding the data accurately.** Please read it carefully and become familiar with all of the definitions, procedures, and notes. Keep it open whenever you are coding.

If you have any questions or challenges during the process of hand-coding, make a note of these and share them with the project manager and/or broader team. If you have any technical problems while using the interface, direct inquiries to Alex Hanna (alex.hanna@gmail.com).

Accessing and Using the MPEDS Annotation Interface

Coding will take place using an online interface designed for this project called the MPEDS Annotation Interface. Each individual has a unique username and password for accessing this system.

- 1) **Open Mozilla Firefox** (DO NOT USE Safari or Google Chrome. These browsers are not compatible with the system)
- 2) **Enter (and bookmark) the website URL:** [LINK REMOVED]
- 3) When prompted, **enter your username and password.** Upon entering the system, **ensure that the system displays your name.** Otherwise you will not be able to receive credit for your work. You will see two ways to access the same articles: The Event Coder Interface and List.

¹ Internal document.

The image shows a simple login interface. At the top, the word 'Login' is displayed in a large, bold font. Below it, there are two input fields. The first is labeled 'Username:' and contains the text 'katie'. The second is labeled 'Password:' and contains a series of asterisks '*****'. At the bottom of the form is a button labeled 'Login'.

- 4) **Select Event Coder Interface.** This is where you will code articles. MPEDS will automatically select and load articles for you. Whenever possible, articles will be clustered and sequenced by university and publication date. There are three panels:
- a) **The Article:** The panel on the left side of the screen contains the article to be analyzed. This is the article you will use to code information. There is a scroll bar that will allow you to view the entire article.
 - b) **Event Descriptions:** The middle panel will eventually contain one or more event descriptions based on your coding of the article, once you save your coding.
 - c) **The Coding Panel:** When you click on “Add event +” on the panel on the right side of the screen, this will open the coding pane. Notice there are four tabs within the coding pane: Basic Info, Yes/No, Text Select, Preset. Those four titles refer to the information you will have to fill out for each of the articles you code. More on these below.
- 5) **List:** To see the list of all the protest events you have coded, go back to the login page and select “List.” There, you’ll see the names and numbers (Article #s) of the articles you have coded. Also you can use the List if you ever realize you need to go back and fix an entry for an event that you already coded.

Every article has an Article #. It appears in the List and in the URL when you have the article open. (The example below is Article 2398.) To go to a specific article, go to:
sheriff.ssc.wisc.edu/campus_protest/event_creator/ARTICLENUMBER

MPEDS Event Creator - Campus Protests Home Logged in as Ellen Logout

Students, members of Williamsburg community conduct protest following Darren Wilson decision

Flat Hat: College of William and Mary | NEWS; Pg. 1 | Amanda Williams | 2014-12-01 | Flat Hat: College of William and Mary_2014-12-01_21

A group in Williamsburg took part in a nationwide event Nov. 25, hosting a Black Lives Matter Protest.

After several speakers addressed those gathered, the march began in front of the College of William and Mary bookstore, traveled down Richmond Road, passed the Sadler center and ended at the Sir Christopher Wren Building.

Travis Harris, a first year American studies Ph.D candidate, opened the protest with 4 minutes and 30 seconds of silence, in solidarity with protests around the country, to commemorate the 4 hours and 30 minutes that Michael Brown, fatally shot by an officer earlier this year, lay in the street. Harris organized the entire event with a future event in mind, tentatively planned for the spring.

"My goal is to have a candid conversation on race here in Williamsburg," Harris said. "My hope is that by having this conversation, each side is going to understand each other better. My end goal is racial reconciliation and peace."

The countrywide protest movement was sparked by the Nov. 24 St. Louis grand jury decision not to indict Darren Wilson, the white police officer who shot Brown, an unarmed, 18-year-old black male. The shooting occurred Aug. 9 in Ferguson, Mo., a suburb of St. Louis. The Williamsburg protest was just one of hundreds from New York to Los Angeles, and stayed peaceful, unlike some others.

Pat Griffith (left) from Williamsburg (with Dr. Marshall Barry '61) said he was at the protest

Event descriptions

Add event +

Basic Info Yes/No Text Select Preset

Provide a short description of this article.

Provide a short description of this event.

Start date

End date

Location (City, State/Province, Country)

Save

Mark Done and Go to Next »

HOW TO READ AN ARTICLE: BASIC STRATEGY

1. Read the entire article
2. Write the article description. If there is NO PROTEST EVENT, record that in the article description.
3. If there IS a PROTEST EVENT, then write an event description and fill out all the other relevant information (in the different tabs).
4. Do the same for each additional event if there are more than one.

Record all the article numbers you code in your internal timesheet.

Overall, the time you spend coding articles will vary based on length of the article and number of events. Articles vary in their format. For example, they may be long in-depth reporting, very short statements, or an opinion or editorial column (expressing openly normative perspective, taking a position, sometimes in the first person). A short article with very little relevant protest information will take much less time to code than a long article with multiple protests. Your goal is to move through these articles quickly, while arbitrating all relevant information to effectively code protest information. Generally, new coders may take up to an hour coding a single article. Once coders are well trained, they tend to take 15 minutes coding an article on average. But this varies from coder to

coder and article to article, as some articles can be coded very quickly and some take much longer. Especially in the beginning, we care more about accuracy than speed.

For almost all articles, you do not need to consult any other sources, and we do not want you to spend your time doing that. However, you may need to on occasion - typically, to check an online map for the geography of an urban campus. Even less often, you might need to search online for the newspaper article to confirm the publication date or to understand text that got displayed in a confusing way.

If You Are Unsure About How To Code an Article

If you have any questions about an article, record your question and the Article # in the [*Coding Questions Google spreadsheet*](#).²

Do not skip an article that you have started coding. The only exception is if you are uncertain about how to code it and need to put it “on hold” until you get feedback from a team leader. In that case, be sure to record the article number in your internal timesheet, so you remember to return to it.

When and How to Fix Errors in Your Coding

Most of the coding errors will be corrected later in this project, when we adjudicate different coders’ codings of the same events and clean the data. However, if you realize that your coding of an article contains an **error** (such as a wrong date), **you didn’t code an event** (and you realized that it was an event from reading another article), or **you didn’t record the right number of events** reported in an article, please go back and fix your coding. To do this, you can **use the pencil icon to edit** the event or **the X icon to delete it**.

If you accidentally close the browser, **the interface saves all the recorded information automatically**. You do not need to click “save.”

² This internal document was used throughout the coding process to track and follow-up on coder questions at our (bi)weekly team meetings.

IDENTIFYING PROTEST EVENTS

If an article is included in this interface, it has been labeled by the haystack classifier of MPEDS as potentially containing a protest. **Your first step is to determine whether there is, in fact, any higher education protest event in this article that meets our definition.** The article is codeable if there are one or more protests that meet our definition.

Definition of protest

For the purposes of this project, a protest is an event organized by one or more people with (1) a date and (2) a location and characterized by (3) one or more actions/forms that differ from routine institutional political participation like voting (e.g., a sit-in, a march) and (4) a collective claim about an issue (e.g., advocating for or against a political goal, expressing the shared grievances of a social group)-- all in an attempt to challenge power relations, change major institutions, pressure institutional leaders, alter law and policy, or otherwise transform society and culture.

Definition of higher education protest

By higher education protests, we mean protests that either are a) geographically located on university and college campuses pertaining to any issue or b) geographically located off campus and pertaining to higher education issues.³ The rationale for this definition is that we are capturing protests that university administrations may be compelled to respond to.

On vs. Off Campus

By “on campus,” we mean the centralized geographic area where classrooms, residences and dining halls are located and where most classes and administrative buildings are located.

“Off-campus” protests about higher education may be about a wide range of issues, including national or state- or provincial-level issues (e.g. provincial education budget cuts that students protest at the capital), issues directly connected to the students’ home campus, or university-owned property outside the geographic campus boundaries, such as university facilities located not on the central campus (e.g. a telescope on a mountain) or a university-affiliated hospital (e.g. University of California system teaching hospitals).

If all or a part of a protest event takes place on campus at any point during the event (e.g., a march

³ Original Footnote: In the U.S., the terms “university” and “college” are often used interchangeably. However, “universities” are typically schools that award 4-year undergraduate degrees and also have graduate programs while “colleges” are typically schools that award 4-year undergraduate degrees (different than colleges in Canada), although colleges might be shorter programs, e.g. for a technical degree. You do not need to know a lot of details about U.S. universities and colleges to do this coding.

from the state Capitol concludes when it reaches campus), it should be coded regardless of whether the issue is connected to higher education or not.

Essential Criteria for Coding an Event:

DATE + LOCATION + either FORM or ISSUE

This is the bare minimum information you must have to code a protest event.

A single protest event could have multiple actions that occur close to each other geographically or one right after the other, like a rally then a sit-in.

When identifying protest events, try to stick to the article's description as much as possible. For instance, if a group of students planned to do a sit-in and then they gathered, but the sit-in never happened because it was interrupted before it occurred, then the event is not a protest and should not be coded.

You should **code every codeable event in every article you read**, even if you have already coded that same event in another article and the information is repetitive. More on this below. The purpose of clustering and sequencing of articles (by university and date) is to give you context, which can help you make sense of reported events. The purpose is not to enable you to skip articles, unfortunately. Later, during the adjudication process, we will decide which articles have useful information and which do not. Please don't make that determination now.

Situations that can make it harder to identify a protest and/or code the article:

It's an "edge case."

It's an edge case if it is difficult to tell if the protest meets our definition. The following edge cases should be coded (so long as they occur on campus or off-campus and are framed as a higher ed issue): Online protest or using phones, routine events by social movements groups (e.g. May Day protest, annual gay pride parade), a religious group preaching hate, or an individual's protest action (such as publicly reading a banned book), chaining oneself to a desk, or carrying a mattress.

A list of demands should be coded as an event if students physically presented demands to administrators, a group/organization sends the demands to the target, and/or there is a mass mobilization with lots of students emailing the demands to a target. We want to avoid coding lists of demands that may have been created just by a single student or that have been posted on social media but not presented to a target with an expectation of a response. Raise these edge cases for discussion with the team if you are not sure.

The journalist and/or the people in the article say things that are confusing.

Not everyone shares the same definition of protest. Protestors sometimes have motivations for not calling their event a protest (e.g. avoiding getting permits) and administrators have motivations for using certain language, too (e.g. calling an action a strike vs. boycott). Sometimes the journalist uses overly vague terms or terms, like “rally”, “strike”, and “boycott” in ways that are different from how we define them. Use your informed judgement. If you identify any confusing language like this, please bring them to discussion with the team. If protestors deny there is a protest happening, but their event fits our criteria for a higher education protest event, you still should code these as protest events.

The article makes vague references to protest.

Articles sometimes make vague references to events like “protests last month” or “protests in 30 cities.” If you can distinguish the essential criteria (DATE + LOCATION + FORM or ISSUE) but there is too little information to identify distinct events, create one single entry. Write a short event description, complete the date and location fields, and code any information you do have based on this vague reference to events. Under Yes/No, you may need to select if the start date is approximate. If you CANNOT distinguish the essential criteria, DO NOT code the event. For petitions and general strikes, for which the start and end date are often unclear and the protest often spans multiple days, dates might be difficult to capture, so do your best to use the information you have available and if necessary select that the date is vague. If the article is satirical, do not code any protest mentioned because it may be false information.

The date of the article and/or protest event seems inaccurate.

Some of the articles in the Lexis-Nexis database have inaccurate publication dates. For example, the publication date may be within our time frame, but the article actually was published 10 or more years ago. If the publication date seems inaccurate, you should Google the article title in quotes + the publication name, i.e. “Americans protest police killings of Blacks” + “The District Chronicles: Howard University”. Still code the event(s) if you are certain that they occur between 2012-2018, and select this box.

If you can't find the article or an explanation in Google, that's fine. Don't spend too much time on this step. If the date is inaccurate and falls outside of the date range, mark the “inaccurate date” and then, in the disqualifying information section, mark the “historical (>1 year) event or outside the date range” box (see below) outside date range” (see below). If you select this option, do not spend time identifying other disqualifying information. If you still have doubts about the article and event, bring it to the team to discuss.

The event is planned or proposed, but it is not clear if it was executed yet.

If this is the case, DO NOT code the event. See the “Reasons to Disqualify” section below.

There are multiple protest events or a complex or confusing event.

If there are multiple protest events, you will code each one separately, even though they are all in the same article. More on this below under the “How to Distinguish Between Events” section. If it is a complex event possibly with additional related events, try to identify the distinct events.

The article reports on a university response but not a codeable protest.

If an article contains university responses to a relevant protest event but does not provide enough information on the event for it to be codeable, you should record the article number in the ‘University Response Articles’ tab in the *Coding Questions*⁴ spreadsheet.

REASONS TO DISQUALIFY

Some events will NOT be coded. In the Yes/No tab, look at the “Disqualifying information” list and consider the bulleted points below, which are all reasons **NOT** to code the event.

Note: If you select *any* of the disqualifying information checkboxes, you will disqualify the **entire article**. If the article reports on multiple events and you identify that one event is not codable according to the codebook criteria, do not code that event. Only use the disqualifying information checkbox(es) when an entire article needs to be dismissed; check all the reasons that apply (if more than one).

There is no protest event.

The protest is geographically off campus with no higher education issue.

Students often participate in protests that are geographically off campus, but if the protest does not involve any higher education issue, then we are NOT coding it. Examples that should not be coded include a Black Lives Matter rally against police racism and violence in Ferguson, Missouri or the

⁴ This internal document was used throughout the coding process to track and follow-up on coder questions at our (bi)weekly team meetings.

Climate Change March (so long as participants in these events do not link their protest issues to higher education).

If individuals are participating in an off-campus protest that is not evidently about higher education but the article quotes or describes them making connections between the issue and higher education and/or their university, then it should be coded (e.g., at a BLM rally, a student says that black students need campus mental health services because they are so stressed about police violence in the community).

The protest is outside Canada or the U.S.

The protest is historical (outside our parameters).

We are not coding events that occurred more than a year before the article was published and/or are outside the date range of the project (2012-2018). We are mostly coding events that have occurred **within a year** of the publication date. If an event is older than that, provide a short description of the article and click “historical (>1 year) event or outside the date range.” This is especially important to do if this is a reference to anything from the Civil Rights era or widely-publicized events that happened multiple years before the article date. Also select this option, and do not code it as a protest event, if the article reports on an event before our time frame of 2012-2018, even if that’s 2011. If the publication date of an article was prior to 2012, don’t bother reading through the article or writing a unique article description. Simply write “**This article was published prior to 2012**” in the article description, select this option under disqualifying information, and quickly move on to the next article.

Exception: If in your judgment as a coder, this is a specific event in the not-too-distant past (say, 18 months before the article date) but still in the 2012-2018 time frame *and* is not likely to have gotten a lot of media coverage (so, unlikely to be in our dataset), you *MAY* code the event. If the protest still is in the 2012-2018 time frame *and* prompted a university response more than a year later, you *SHOULD* code the event (so we can easily link that protest to the response in our dataset) .

The information on the protest is overly vague.

You should **not** code the event if you cannot distinguish the essential criteria of DATE+LOCATION+FORM or ISSUE and some key points are still really unclear, e.g. all you know is: “students protested last week over their complaints.” Use your informed discretion.

This is a duplicate article.

If you have already encountered the exact same article, select this option. If a few sentences are different, then still code it.

The event is one of the following actions. None of these are codeable protest events.

- Memorial services and commemorations of historic protests or past protest leaders, such as the civil rights March on Washington (with no accompanying contemporary protest). (Commemorations that involve a protest action like a vigil or march and concern a political/historic event, such as the Armenian genocide, should be coded).
- Individual grievances, crimes, and public displays of anger (mobs) that are not expressive of either the social goals or the shared grievances of a social category/group (such as a riot following the outcome of a sports match).
- Isolated crimes, lawsuits, court cases, policy decisions that do not include expressions of a broader group or collective goal.
- Political campaign events.
- Violence or vandalism, such as graffiti, unrelated to any protest form.
- Press conference or news conference by a governmental or institutional organization (i.e. elected official, political candidate, or university official).
- Routine meetings or town halls hosted by student government.
- Routine politics, campaigns, speeches by elected officials or those seeking electoral office.
- Interviews and speeches by celebrities.
- Charity action without policy demands (collect money).
- Personal actions (e.g. crime, personal expression), self-expression (purpose of event is entirely inward, not outward).
- A party or religious ritual without making a claim, expressing a grievance, or advocating for/against policy change.
- Acts of terrorism - intentionally destroying large amounts of property or injuring people.
- Workshops
- Planned events or events that are mentioned to happen in the future, but they have not taken place yet.

HOW TO CODE AN ARTICLE WITH NO CODEABLE PROTESTS

You will code minimal information:

1. In the “Basic Info” tab: provide a **brief general description of the article** with a brief explanation of why the article is disqualified and also why you think the interface selected this article.
2. In the “Yes/No” tab: Under the “Disqualifying information” section, **select ALL the options that apply** to the article. [Click here](#) for an example.

USING INFORMATION FROM PREVIOUS ARTICLES

If an event is mentioned in an article without lots of details but you have knowledge of the event from a prior article, you can use that knowledge to inform your coding (esp. if it is not clear if an event occurred). However, do this minimally and **only** use **essential** information from the previous article. **Only** use prior information for one or more of the following:

- to record start and/or end date
- to record issue or form
- to record location
- to confirm if a codeable event happened (e.g., record target if necessary to confirm it is a higher ed protest and to keep coding accurate)
- to differentiate between events

Also, in the article description, you should mention that you are using information from a previous article to inform your coding. In the article description, **make sure you specify what info you are using from previous articles (eg. issue), and try to include the article number that informs your judgement.** Make sure that your knowledge about the event is correct. double-check the information that you have if you are not certain. For an example, [click here](#).

If the article you’re coding has a protest and protestors make passing reference to protests at the University of Missouri but the article is missing key information that we already know (such as the date), code Mizzou as an event and related protest but spend minimal time on that; for our analysis, what we care about is just that Mizzou was referenced; we have better details elsewhere.

WHEN AN ARTICLE REPORTS ON MULTIPLE PROTEST EVENTS

How To Distinguish Between Events

Some articles report on multiple discrete protest events. These “events” can be large and complex and may involve different subgroups of people doing different things or being in different places, so you will need to pay close attention to those. It is often hard to make these distinctions. The protestors might engage in multiple forms of protest, e.g., a rally followed by a sit-in with a press conference; that would be one protest event.

Create separate events when you can identify important characteristics and meaningful elements that differentiate one event from another. As long as there is sufficient detail to code (date, place, action or issue), create a new entry for each of these events (click on the Add event +). Be sure to answer all sections of all the tabs for each entry completely, even if there is some duplicate information. Mention the complex set of actions or actors in the description of the event.

If there is a complex event with multiple things happening in roughly the same location but no distinction among groups/organizations at the event, just code it all as one event. If the events are related to each other (part of a larger campaign or response from one group to another group), include one or more sentences in the event description about how the events are related to each other. Capture the multiple participating groups and the context.

Common Situations that Should Be Coded as Distinct Events

- Different activist groups hold different protest events in the same location.
- Simultaneous protests taking place at different campuses within the same school system, e.g. protests at University of Toronto St. George and University of Toronto Mississauga
- Activists organize similar events around the same issue in different locations, e.g. coordinated rallies about prison abolition on campuses in multiple cities which are explicitly named.
- The same group organizes multiple protests for different dates.
- A protest for one issue and a counter-protest for the other side of the issue (i.e. protest against Islamophobia and a counter-protest that is anti-immigrant).
- A big rally where most people peacefully demonstrated, but a subgroup broke off and went around breaking windows. Note this in the event description for each entry.

- A five-day protest caravan driving between cities with rallies at 10 different cities along the way. In this case, code each rally that you have enough information on as a distinct event and note in the event description for each that it is part of a 5-day caravan.

Here is what the screen looks like after you have saved two events:

When There Are Repeated Non-Contiguous Protests

You may come across protest events that take place on a regular basis as part of a protest movement, but that are non-contiguous (i.e. there are breaks between when the events happen), such as nightly marches. These are typically events with the same form. This is not especially common; we have primarily seen it with the daily Quebec student strikes and the athlete anti-racism strikes at games or practice. There should be some logic to the repetition, e.g. “every Monday” or “every game.” But, it can be tricky to code because the article does not specify every single date (which would make many or most of the protests too vague to code) or because coding all the non-contiguous events would be very time-consuming and repetitive as all your entries would have the same event description, text select, and preset information. The purpose of this divergence from our standard protocol is to prevent you from having to perform the time-consuming task of creating a separate entry for each of the events when most or all of the events reported on in the article have the same information.

When to follow this rule: Code all of the non-contiguous events as one event if an article ...

- 1) reports on this type of protest having more than two non-contiguous events,
- 2) does not provide information that differentiates each event from one another, and
- 3) has an approximate or definite start date.

How to code: In the date fields, enter the date of the first event as the start date and the date of the last event as the end date. In the article description, make sure you use the term “non-contiguous” events, note how often they are repeated (e.g., daily, weekly, every practice), and make clear that you are following these guidelines.

In the case that an article provides distinguishing information for *some* of the non-contiguous events, you should still code all of the events under one entry according to the instructions above, but also make a separate entry for the event(s) that have distinguishing information. Take, for example, an article that reports on 10 days of nightly marches against tuition hikes and mentions that protestors also destroyed property and were tear gassed by police on the 10th day of the marches, but does not provide any distinguishing information on the previous 9 marches. You should code all of the 10 marches under one entry and only include information in the coding that was common between all of the events (so, you **would not** include the information on the property destruction and police actions under this entry). Then, also code the 10th nightly march in a separate entry and include the distinguishing information under this entry (so, you **would** include the information on property destruction and police actions under this entry).

Again, if you code an article based on the instructions in this section, be sure to make this clear in the article description.

CODING NOTEWORTHY PROTEST EVENTS

Some protests are very noteworthy and have been frequently reported on in student newspapers across the US and Canada due to their newsworthiness, their impact, the fact that they took place at a prominent university/college, etc. Because these events are reported on so often, journalists often leave out essential information about the events (such as their date, location, etc.) because they assume the reader has a baseline knowledge of the event(s). But, as a result of this lack of information, these event mentions are often not codeable.

When these noteworthy protest events are reported on, but some essential information is missing, you should gather this information from the *Notable Protest Events Spreadsheet*.⁵ You should use the information on the event contained in the spreadsheet to fill in the information missing from the article and code the event. Almost always, the information that will be missing is the date. When you use information from the spreadsheet to inform your coding, you should note this clearly in the

⁵ Internal document. Contained data for: University/Location, Location, Event, Start Date, End Date, Form, Issue, Racial Issue, Target, Articles Used for Start Date, Articles Used for Form, Articles Used for Target, Notes.

Article Description. You should also specify exactly what information you gathered from the spreadsheet in the Event Description.

The following is a running list of the events⁶ contained in the Notable Protest Events Spreadsheet, and information on how to code these unique events.

1. Protests against the administration at the University of Missouri from October 2015 to November 2015 over the administration's handling of racist incidents on campus. The events include:
 - Protest at the homecoming parade
 - Jonathon Butler's hunger strike
 - University of Missouri football team's protest
 - Because these protests were so noteworthy, some articles use very vague language when referring to the events, such as "recent anti-racism protests at Mizzou." When articles refer to the Mizzou protest events in this way, and do not report on any one specific protest event, you should **not** code any of the events.
 - Oftentimes, the article will report on specific events that took place at Mizzou. There are two ways that an article can refer to a specific protest event that took place:
 - 1) The article refers to the form of the event
 - *Example: the football players' strike*
 - 2) The article refers to the name of the event (without mentioning the form)
 - *Example: the homecoming parade protest*

In these situations, as long as you are sure that the article is referring to the 2015 anti-racism protests at the University of Missouri (and not a protest at Mizzou from another time period) you **should** code the event, and gather any missing information that you need to code the event from the *Notable Protest Event Spreadsheet*.⁷ This means that for the second class of these cases noted above (in which the article refers to the name of the event without mentioning the form), you should code the article and gather all relevant information, including the form of the event, from the Notable Protest Event Spreadsheet.

Athlete Strike vs. Athlete Boycott

Oftentimes, journalists and protestors use the terms 'boycott' and 'strike' interchangeably to refer to protest actions in which individuals refrain from engaging in some specific activity. Sometimes, the use of these terms by protestors and journalists to describe protest activities are not consistent with our project definitions for 'boycott' and 'strike.' The most prominent example of this is the reporting

⁶ In reality this did not become a running list, as the only protests contained in this internal spreadsheet were for the University of Missouri protests in 2015 (bullet #1). However, we did create instructions for other notable events (see the section of this document titled "Instructions for Unique Protests").

⁷ Internal document. Contained data for: University/Location, Location, Event, Start Date, End Date, Form, Issue, Racial Issue, Target, Articles Used for Start Date, Articles Used for Form, Articles Used for Target, Notes.

on the University of Missouri football players' protest. In situations like this, you should privilege the language used by the protestors, and code the event according to their description of the event as a boycott or a strike. If the protestors' first-hand description of the event is not provided in the article, or is not clear, you should use the journalist's description of the event (which tends to be "boycott").

If you come across an article that you are unsure about (ex/ the article does not provide the protestors' description of the event, the journalist refers to the event as a strike, but it seems clear to you that the event is a boycott, and not a strike) you should bring the article to the attention of the team.

THE CODING TABS

If you've determined that you definitely should code a protest event, go through all four tabs.

Be sure to consider every single question and complete all that you have information on. It is important that our information is as systematic as possible. You will need to refer to the article multiple times through this process.

Basic Info Tab

You should complete all the fields on this tab:

Article Description

Try to start your description in the following way: *The article describes...* or *The op-ed/editorial describes...* Article descriptions should include:

- **the broader issue** is that the protest event relates to and **who is doing what** (major actors, including but not only the protestors) as well as any organization/coordination the protest group had with any other groups.
- **the form and issue** for the event(s). If the article only provides the form and not the issue, or only the issue and not the form, mention this.
- If the article reports on **multiple events**, mention this and what the article is talking about generally (the event description of each event will be specific to those events). When you create coding entries for each of those events, you can cut and paste the same article description.

Other information you *might* need to include in the article description:

- **Formal demands:** If the article reports on an event that includes a formal demand or list of demands, mention this explicitly and use the exact language “list of demands” or “demand(s)” if this applies (it’s important to use this exact language because we are going to search for these terms in later stages of analysis on the project). Also, you should try to briefly explain the demand(s) in the article description, and go much more in-depth about the demands in the event description. If the event is a commemoration, mention this.
- **Confusion about on or off campus:** If the article is unclear whether the protest took place on or off-campus, mention this. If the article does not explicitly state where the protest took place but provides information that suggests that it took place on campus, off-campus, or on and off-campus, include this info here.
- **Op-Eds:** Note in the article description that the article is an “opinion” or “editorial” or “op-ed.” If you’re not certain if it’s an op-ed or not, use your discretion or default to op-ed.
- **Anything significant about the how the article is written:** If the reporting is very vague or something else about the writing really stands out (e.g. very long with lots of events, a lack of clear dates, a historical retrospective), note that here. You don’t have to do this for every article. If you know that the article is one in a related series, note that.

For examples, [click here](#).

Event Description

Event descriptions may range anywhere from 1 sentence to 8 sentences, or in some cases, even more. The length of the event description depends entirely on the complexity of the event and the details provided in the article. If you find a great sentence or a few sentences from the article summarizing the event, you can cut and paste that. Describe...

- **Who** - actors (e.g. “students,” names of organizations)
- **What they do** - form(s) plus a bit more detail than you capture elsewhere, also include any symbols/slogans,
- **Where** - include names of key places like a building name. If the protest moves, such as moving across a single campus, moving off-campus, or moving across campuses, mention this. If protests occurred in multiple locations, note that, e.g. “across the province of Quebec,” “system-wide,” “throughout New York State,” or “in Buffalo, Albany, and New Paltz.”
- **Why** - state the issue and target, plus a bit more detail than you capture elsewhere. There are two especially important points to include, if relevant:
 - **if the event is a solidarity protest.** In these cases, you should try to copy and paste the article text that indicates that the event is a solidarity protest. Definition of solidarity protest: something is a solidarity protest if the journalist and/or protestors describe the event as a display of “solidarity;” sometimes related terms are used, such as support, unity, standing with, or inspired by. Protestors may be

showing solidarity with protestors and/or events elsewhere (which is our primary interest in this) or with a cause or something else

- **the presentation/issuing of any formal demand or list of demands** for policy or institutional change. Mention this and use the language of “demand”/“demanded”/“list of demands” explicitly. State the demands made by protestors, and, if available, their targets. If the demands are extremely long and detailed, you can summarize them.
- **When** usually is not necessary unless you need to clarify something like the timing/movement of the event

If the article only reports on one event, the article description and the event description might be similar; try to use the description of the event to be more specific, such as describing how many students participated, what they did, how they did it, for how long, and any important slogans.

For examples, [click here](#).

Date of the Event

Format: year-month-day. You can also use the calendar option. The calendar defaults to the present date, but you can enter part of a date (e.g. 2012-08 to get it to August 2012). If you enter the article date in the box and then click on the calendar, you will often be able to figure out the event date from these references and the calendar. For a one-day event, the start and end dates are the same.

Often the article will use phrases like “Tuesday” or “last week”. You may need to use the article date (shown under the article title) along with info in the text to pin down the date.

If the article gives you a week range, assume Sunday is the first day of the week. If the article mentions a month but not the date, record the first of the month as the approximate date, e.g. 2017-01-01 for January, 2017. If you are uncertain of the end date, or the article suggests that the event is ongoing, leave the end date blank. If you cannot discern an exact date (but know enough about the date to code the article), make a note of that in the article description. In the Yes/No tab, there are a few checkboxes about dates you may need to complete; more on this below.

If the article only gives you an approximate date range that is extremely vague (ex/ “last semester” or “earlier this year”), then in the Yes/No tab, you should select “Disqualifying Information-> overly vague”, and you should **NOT** code the event.

Location of the Event

Enter the location (city, state/province, country) of the event. For an example, [click here](#).

If there are events in multiple municipalities, see Yes/No below.

If the Event Doesn't Have a Physical/Geographic Location

For events that are online, rely on phones, or other events that do not have a physical geographic location - we recognize that the location is more complicated; we will never know exactly where participants are when they engage. In these cases, write "Virtual" in the "Location" field if there is no geographic/physical location of the protest and/or some protest forms (e.g. a letter writing campaign, December dial, online-only petitions). Only code virtual protests if they concern a higher ed issue or if students physically gather/act on campus, e.g. 14117.

Yes/No Tab

Is the start date exact or approximate?

Click whether the date is exact or you are estimating it.

Does this event span one day or more than one day?

Click whether the event is a one-day event or a multi-day event.

Disqualifying information?

Double check the "Disqualifying information" options. Select any that apply. See above instructions if you select any of those options.

Does this event...

Consider each of these options:

Occur off-campus with a higher ed. issue

Check this if the protest geographically occurs **entirely** off-campus and is clearly related to higher education issues, such as campus sexual assault at their university, campus police misconduct across the country, government funding for higher education, or university-owned property. **Do not** select this option if the protest takes place on and

off-campus. For more details, see “off campus with no higher education issue” under Disqualifying Information above.

No student involvement

Select this option if there is no explicit or implicit reference to college or university students participating in the event. These are normally events by and for non-student groups such as faculty, staff, Westboro church activists, and White supremacists. If even just one student is mentioned as being present, that is considered student involvement so do not select this option.

Occur in multiple cities

The primary function of this checkbox is to indicate when a protest event is awkward to geocode. This happens in two situations.

- 1) If protestors organized a single protest to happen in multiple municipalities - *e.g. a march crosses from one town to another, a CUPE strike at all three of UofT’s campuses (so, the three municipalities are Toronto, Mississauga, and Scarborough).*
- 2) If the protest takes place at multiple schools or is part of a system-wide protest and we know the location for at least one of the schools - *e.g. Faculty at UC Davis led a system-wide walkout in protest of working conditions. Three other schools in the UC system participated in the event.*
- 3) If there are protests on multiple campuses but we don’t know any of the locations - *e.g. 14 schools in Georgia held a walk-out in protest of a state bill.*

How to code the location for these events:

- 1) If protestors organize one event to occur in multiple municipalities including the location of the article’s newspaper, enter that same city/town as the location. Also, in the Yes/No tab, you should select ‘*Does this event->Occur in multiple cities;*’ and note the locations in the event description.
- 2) Occasionally, a protest event is system-wide, province-wide, state-wide, nationally, occurring in both the U.S. and Canada, or otherwise involving multiple municipalities and the article does not specify any of the municipalities (e.g. “*Students participated in protests throughout the University of California system*” or “*Protests happened across universities in Quebec*”). This is unusual and most likely to come up when the publishing university is not participating in the protest. Follow these guidelines to determine a location and also select “occur in multiple cities.”
 - If an article names the university or college system, use that system’s flagship location (you may need to Google it). If not, use the capital of the state or province.

- 3) If one or more individual universities are named *and* it is a event occurring in multiple cities, code each protest at each named university as a separate event (if you have the essential criteria) and select text referencing the system-wide event or protest on other campuses as “related protest on other campuses;” It is very likely you should also code these sorts of events as campaigns.

Contains direct quotes

Check this if there are direct quotes from protesters or university officials.

Contains slogans or other protest symbols

Check this if a protest uses slogans (e.g. “No racist police”) or symbols (e.g. flags being used to convey a political position, particular colours such as red dresses to represent Missing and Murdered Indigenous Women, specific songs that are part of a protest action/form such as Black National Anthem, or protestors wearing particular colours). Also select for specific songs that are part of a protest action/form such as Black National Anthem) used by protestors. Capture a hashtag only if it’s also a prominent slogan (e.g. #BlackLivesMatter, #MeToo), but do not capture hashtags that are not used as slogans (typically, that happens when protestors share a hashtag to get other people to use it on social media).

Part of a larger campaign (within a university or across universities)

A campaign is a series of sustained, targeted political actions with a common goal around the same issue and occurring at a university or involving multiple universities around the city, region, country, or world. The campaign can involve one single group or multiple groups. If the campaign involves more than one group/movement/organization, only select this option if the coordination happens between identifiable groups or organizations. These political actions are often intentionally coordinated protest events but could be actions such as a letter-writing campaign.

Select this checkbox if **the coordination is explicitly mentioned** in the article or if you know about it from other articles. Campaigns may be:

- One action in a larger set of protest actions at a single university (e.g. campaign for a policy change at one university, such as a sustained effort by a student organization to get the university to divest from fossil fuels)
- Coordinated with protests by students, faculty, and/or staff from multiple colleges and universities. The protests could be organized by the same movement organization such as United Students Against Sweatshops, the mattress protests, environment divestment campaigns.

Don’t select this checkbox if the event is only a solidarity protest but not explicitly coordinated. Don’t assume it was a campaign even if similar events happened in

different places around the same time. Try to stick to the protesters' description of the event to assess this criteria.

Ritualized or cyclical

These are events linked to some regular patterns of holding events, not to some recent precipitating event. Examples include the annual Gay Pride march, Take Back the Night, or a commemoration of some past event.

Counter-protest

A counterprotest could be either of the following, regardless of what the counter-protesters say they're doing:

- *a protest in opposition to the original protest and/or action* (e.g., a protest objecting to another group's decision to invite a controversial speaker). With these, the counter-protesters usually have a target (e.g., the original protest group, an invited speaker).
- *a reactionary protest* aiming to show a different position than another protest (e.g. pro-Israel rally next to pro-Palestinian event, pro-police event at the same time as a Black Lives Matter event). With these, there's often no target, i.e. counter-protesters do not identify anyone as their opposition, not even the original protest.

A counter-protest may occur at a different place or time than the main protest, but usually within the same day. Code it as its own event.

If there are two protests and one is likely a counterprotest but it's not clear from the reporting, just code them both as protests and note this issue in the article description, e.g. 14604. Revised 5/2023: See adjudication guidelines.

For an example on how to select these options, [click here](#).

Text Select Tab

(for definitions of these categories)

Here, you will highlight information in the article relevant to each of the topics list, then click on the + and that information will be listed under the topic. Be sure to consider every single option. It is OK to skip things if nothing is mentioned. For each of the categories below, relevant text should be selected separately, e.g. if a protest has multiple actions/forms, select each of those separately.

You will select a small amount of text for some topics and lots of text (if available) for others, as explained here. For Form, Issues, and Target, the text you select will correspond to checkboxes in the Preset Tab; more on this below.

For examples, [click here](#).

Actions/forms

These are the protest actions that people engage in (e.g., rally, protest, demonstrate, petition, boycott - see definitions below under Preset Tab). Sometimes there is one action in a protest event, and sometimes there are multiple actions that occur close to each other geographically or one right after the other, like a rally then a sit-in. Think of this as corroboration of the checkboxes in the Preset Tab -- e.g., the text is evidence that it's a demonstration-- plus a little bit of specificity.

We are interested in knowing the general form of the protest, not the specific actions that were part of the event. For example, text select "demonstration" or "picketing" if the article includes those words instead of "students held signs for 15 minutes." If there is only vague text about the protestors' actions, e.g. "students gathered," select that. Select minimal text because details should be in the protest event description. For examples, [click here](#).

The language that participants use to describe protest actions is politicized and contentious. If there is disagreement about the form among the protestors or between protestors and other people (e.g. university officials), default to the language that the protestors use. However, there is an exception for protest actions in which student athletes refuse to practice or play: code these as "strikes" (even if the participants or journalists refer to their actions as a boycott). Our reasoning is that a boycott is a refusal to consume a product/service while a strike is a refusal to provide a product/service.

Actors [Protest Participants]

Individuals or categories of people (students, workers, protesters, professors, U.S. student government associations, staff, administrators, government officials) participating in the protest. Include **names and titles/roles** if identified in the article. Sometimes, the article will mention the name of the person and their title or role in separate places in the article. In this case, add the name of the individual and their title in the '[Persons Freeform](#)' box. If actors are using a pseudonym, only select under this category if you can also capture text that states that the actor is using a pseudonym. University departments and schools, e.g. the Department of Sociology, are considered actors (do not select them under Movement Organizations. For examples, [click here](#)).

Government officials

Named individuals who are elected and holding office or appointed officials of government agencies. Usually, these are individuals with no other relationship to the university and they are named in the article as government officials. Only code those government officials who have participated in, commented on, or otherwise reacted to the protest event or who are targets of the protest (if they are a target, also select them using the Target text select). Former government officials should only be selected here if the protest is related to their actions in their former capacity

as a government official. Select relevant Indigenous government officials under this category, and make sure to select text that clearly indicates that the individual is an Indigenous government official.

If the article makes reference to government officials who have nothing to do with the protest, then they shouldn't be coded. If you are not clear on this, it is better to overselect. When in doubt, consider that the purpose of this field is to capture the dynamics of responses, e.g., if a high level government official makes a comment, that may suggest the protestors are getting broader attention and possibly being impactful (although of course this depends on the journalist, too).

Include **names and titles/roles** if identified in the article. Sometimes, the article will mention the name of the person and a few lines below their title or role. In this case, enter the name of the individual and their title in the '[Persons Freeform](#).' For examples, [click here](#).

Occasionally, people have complicated roles and should be selected for multiple categories. For example, Janet Napolitano was appointed head of the University of California system and was formerly head of the U.S. Dept of Homeland Security. She should be selected both as government and university official.

Issues

These are what the protest is about and/or the reason(s) why people are protesting. It's the core matter at hand. Think of this as **corroboration** of the checkboxes in the Preset Tab--e.g., the text is evidence that it's a labor issue-- plus a little bit of specificity. The goal is about 1-3 chunks of text (a word or a few words) per event.

Include any important **actions or events that inspired or triggered** the protest (e.g., a police shooting, a university president's email, another protest event that protestors are showing solidarity with). This also includes a **call to action and/or coordination that triggers/inspires the protest** (e.g., students responding to a call to action by students at the University of Missouri by dressing in black to show solidarity).

If the issue is not entirely clear or is not agreed upon by those on opposing sides (e.g hate speech vs free speech, pro-life vs abortion access/pro-choice), default to the view of the protestors, as they articulate it.

Select each issue separately rather than selecting many together (if they're in a list). Avoid selecting parts of people's quotes because that can be confusing. Try to select text that describes what's going on (vs. quotes that express an opinion). Try to select phrases or else, if necessary, select complete sentences. Sometimes, there really is not any text to corroborate the Preset checkbox, e.g. an anti-racism protest where the issue of racism is understood, preachers on milk crates telling students they are sinners; for these, note in the article description the issue is vague. For examples [click here](#).

Movement organizations

Specific named political and/or non-governmental organizations, including student groups, that have sponsored, organized, or participated in the event. Some movement organizations have the same name as their slogan, most prominently Black Lives Matter, Fight for \$15, and divestment campaigns. If a participant is identified as a member of an organization but it is not clear if the organization is actually participating, still select the organization (this will help Ellen and Alex to identify possible overlapping networks of activists). If the article mentions or includes quotes from a sympathetic (or critical) individual from an organization not directly involved in the event, do not code that. University departments and schools, e.g. the Department of Sociology, are not movement organizations and should be coded as Actors.

Include Canadian student unions as well as named “student unions” in the U.S. that actually are student organizations, like a Black Students Union. Do not include U.S. student governments. For examples, [click here](#).

(Other) Participating universities

The names of university and university systems participating in the protest, if not only the publishing university (i.e. from the university that published that newspaper). Importantly, this category is used differently depending on whether or not protestors are from the publishing university:

- If protestors are only from the publishing university, **do not** use this category.
- If protestors are from the publishing university *and* one or more other universities or university systems, select the names of *all* the relevant institutions. For example: if the Harvard Crimson reports on a protest involving Harvard students, MIT students, and students from SUNY (the New York State system), select “Harvard,” “MIT,” and “SUNY.”
- If protestors are from other universities or university systems but not the publishing university, select the names of those other institutions. For example, if the Harvard Crimson reports on a protest with only MIT students, select “MIT.”

Police actions

The activities of the security forces mentioned in the article who are related to the event and the things they did at the event, e.g. present at the event, monitor the event, make arrests. Also select any quotes from security forces. Use this for government police and university police/campus security. With each text selection, try to capture enough content so we can tell who did what--either the campus police or the government police (e.g. “the campus police were present”); capture

complete sentences whenever possible. When in doubt, overselect the potentially relevant text. You do not need to code specific names of individuals. For examples, [click here](#).

Property damage

When people, both protestors and bystanders, destroy or deface property. For examples [click here](#).

Part of protest occurs off-campus

When a protest event geographically spans on and off campus, e.g., if an event has a rally on campus then a march to an off-campus site, like the police department, code that as all the same event and select all of the actions that take place off-campus under this category. Select the text that indicates the off-campus geographic location(s), i.e. where they are, and as well as some text indicating what they did off-campus. For examples, [click here](#).

Related protests involving other universities

Select text on related protest actions that have occurred involving other colleges/universities. This may be another event which you are going to code for this article. You should select text under this category for all of the related events. The selected text should indicate the connection between the events (in many cases you will have to select the same text for each event).

Under this text select, you should always select related events that are on a university campus. You should only select related events that are off-campus when the article indicates (implicitly or explicitly) that students from other universities are participating.

We are using this category broadly, to try to capture the range of ways that multiple universities and multiple protests may be connected to or relevant for each other. For example, protests may be related across universities because

- Protestors on one campus seem to be taking inspiration from protests on another campus,
- Protestors on one campus say they are showing solidarity with another campus,
- Protestors on different campuses appear to be or definitely are coordinating their activities,
- Other possible relationships

Whether or not you are coding the other protest(s) as a separate event: highlight complete sentences (typically a few sentences, more if necessary) that indicate the names of other universities/colleges, references to other schools without names, the relationship between events, the form, the target(s), and the timing/date if available. Some examples:

- “demonstrators gathered on the [Univ of Michigan] Diag in solidarity with Missouri's Black community.”(#4552)
- “Incidents at the University of Missouri sparked similar protests at colleges around the nation, including Yale University, Howard University, Claremont McKenna College, Boston University, Georgetown University, Purdue University, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, Emory University, Ithaca College and others.”
- “This event was part of the SUNY Walk Out that same day.” (If there are protests at 3 SUNY universities and you code each one as an event, this could be the text you select for this category for all three.)
- “Five schools across Indiana also participated in the Day of Action.”
- “Students across Quebec are striking.”

Under this category, also select text that indicates protestors’ first hand perspective on the connection between the events or issues elsewhere and local issues they are concerned with.

Example:

- “Voices are being silenced not only in Missouri, but right here at the University of Michigan,’ said Social Work student Wendy Cortes, one of the event's organizers.” #4552

For further examples, [click here](#).

Size

Specific references to how many people are involved as actors in the protest event - the size of the group of protestors. These may be specific numbers (e.g. “over 70 people”), or they may be phrases like “a small group” or “dozens” or “a large group” or “a crowd.” If the size numbers change as the event moves, capture all the size numbers reported that are relevant. For examples, [click here](#).

Slogans or other protest symbols

Select any slogans (e.g. “No racist police”) or symbols (e.g. a flag being used to convey a political position, particular colours such as red dresses to represent Missing and Murdered Indigenous Women, specific songs that are part of a protest action/form such as Black National Anthem) used by protestors, if reported. Text select all that apply, along with some explanation of the meaning of a symbol if included; it is okay to be overly inclusive. Capture a hashtag only if it’s also a prominent slogan (e.g. #BlackLivesMatter, #MeToo), but do not capture hashtags that are not used as slogans (typically, that happens when protestors share a hashtag to get other people to use it on social media).

Target

Who or what entity are the protesters opposing? This should be one or more specific named individuals, named offices (e.g. “the president”), and/or named organizations, including names of universities. Think of this as corroborating the target selection(s) on the Preset list. The target is different from the audience of the protest, although this can be difficult to differentiate. For example, a protest against police violence targets the police, even if the protest interrupts a university event and the immediate audience is the people attending the university event.

Look out for named entities or general bodies that are asked to do something, e.g. Oakland City Council, the grand jury, legislators.

Differentiating an individual target from an organizational target: If protestors are opposing an administrator/government official regarding a specific policy or action, then “university” or “domestic government” is at least one of the targets (not a specific entity within a university/government, like the Board of Trustees); be sure to also use Text Select to record the policy or action as an issue. However, if the protest is about the individual’s past actions prior to their official role as a university/government official, calls for their resignation, calls for their apology, or calls for individual actions apart from their official duties (ex/ release of their birth certificate), then at least one target is the individual. For example, asking for someone’s resignation versus just occupying their office because of some administrative decision or issue.

For examples of text select for target, [click here](#).

There are some situations when you should **not** text select a target (you will indicate this with the Target Preset-> No target):

- If the protestors are just trying to change what other general, unspecified people think about an issue or how they act (e.g. preachers condemning any and all LGBTQ+ students but not singling out particular students or student groups).
- If protestors simply are standing in solidarity with a protest elsewhere (an “inspiration” protest) and are not explicitly targeting their own administration, the target of the inspiration protest, or any other entity in any way.

However, if the protestors are standing in solidarity but also targeting their own administration, select the protestor’s university as the target. If the protestors are standing in solidarity and are also explicitly targeting the same target as the “inspiration” protest, and/or the protestors are supporting demands that the “inspiration” protest are making of their target, select the “inspiration” protest’s target as the target.

Other university where protest occurred

The name of the university where the protest occurs if any of the following are true:

- the protest takes place at a university other than the one which the newspaper is sourced from. For example, if a University of Toronto newspaper reports on a protest at York University, you should select York University.
- the protest takes place at the publishing university *and* another university. For example, if Ryerson's newspaper reports on a protest that moves from Ryerson to University of Toronto, select both schools.
- the unusual situation when a protest takes place at another school but both schools share the same campus. For example, if York's newspaper reports on an event at the Seneca college campus at York, select Seneca.

Alex and Ellen will use this to geocode the location. For examples, [click here](#).

University officials

Named individuals, offices or entities which represent the university and are somehow relevant to the protest event. This would include administrators, spokespeople, and faculty in positions which direct university policy (but don't just include any faculty member mentioned). When coding, **include names and titles/roles** if identified in the article. Sometimes, the article will mention the name of the person and a few lines below their title or role. In this case, add the name of the individual and their title in the ['Person's Freeform'](#) box. For examples, [click here](#).

University responses

Highlight all text on the university or universities' responses to the protest(s) - meaning, their actions in anticipation of, in reaction to the protest and/or in support of the protest. The actors may be named or unnamed university officials or named or unnamed units, e.g. the administration or the Department of Sociology. Depending on the article, this may be a lot of text compared to other Text Select categories. The text you select may include:

- quotes and who said them,
- the universities' position on the event. This often is what a university official says or the article's paraphrasing (e.g., calling the protest a unreasonable disruption),

- what a different university or officials from another university said about a protest taking place at a different university, or reactions they had to a protest at a different university (e.g. article #11939: university officials from UofT react to a protest that took place at McGill),
- the universities' efforts to prevent a protest
- the universities' tactical reactions to a protest (e.g. an official speaks to protestors directly),
- what the university *says* it will do regarding protestors' demands and grievances,
- programmatic and policy changes that the university actually implements,
- text noting that the university has *not* responded (avoidance is a response),
- press statements and other formal announcements (e.g. update on the status of an investigation) from the campus police. These press statements or formal announcements should also be selected under 'Police Actions.' However, you do not need to text select the **actions** of campus police here, those should only be captured under 'Police Actions.'
- and other content you see as appropriate.

Remember that **selecting more is better than less**, so try to capture as much as you can. It could be a lot. For examples, [click here](#).

Violence/attack against protestors by bystanders

Descriptions of people *other than the police* engaging in physical violence or attempts at physical violence against protestors (not verbal threats). If the police are hurting the protestors, *do not code that here*; that would be police actions. If counter-protestors are hurting the protestors, you would code that under the separate event for the counter-protest. If the reporting is vague about who was engaging in violence, select that all that could apply.

Violence/attack against persons by protestors

Descriptions of protestors engaging in physical violence or attempting physical violence against others (not verbal threats). This includes violence towards police. If the reporting is vague about who was engaging in violence, select all that could apply. For examples, [click here](#).

Persons Freeform

This textbox should **only** be used to code non-contiguous titles and names of individuals, i.e. their name and their title/description are not in the same sentence or in adjoining sentences. Any individual included in this textbox must be codeable in at least one of the following categories:

Actors, Target, University Officials, or Government Officials; do not include individuals who are not relevant for coding purposes. For any individual that you include in this textbox, you should also select their name under the corresponding Text Select category (either Actors, Target, University Officials, or Government Officials). Coders should use this text box to type out the following information for these people following this exact formatting; don't include the year of student graduation (e.g. '18):

Template:

- *Proper Name/Title [at/of] Institution Name*
- *Proper Name/Title 1 [at/of] Institution 1; Title 2 [at/of] Institution 2*

Examples:

- *Jay Inslee/Governor of the State of Washington*
- *Michelle Lin/Student at Concordia University; President of Divest Concordia; Member of Concordia Student Union*

Here is what the "Text Select" Page looks like after some information has been coded.

PRESET TAB

(for definitions of checklist options)

On the Preset tab, you **categorize the event based on its Form, Issues, Racial Issues, and Target**. Within each of those categories, you can select more than one. Remember that the issues coded should be what the protesters or the article consider or mention as an issue, not what it is implied from the descriptions. This is often difficult. Do your best.

About the interface: Some of these lists are long. If you click the header for General Issue, Racial Issue, or Target and then you want the sublist under that header to collapse again, you might need to click Form.

Form

A codeable protest must have a form or issue. If you do not know the form of the event, then you **do not** select any option. Select all that apply. For an example on how the “form” preset option works, [click here](#).

- **Blockade/slowdown/disruption** - Actions that intentionally impede or slow down the normal course of events.
- **Boycott** - A refusal to consume or use a product/service. It can include refusing to participate in a specific activity (e.g. eating at a campus restaurant, attending class) or refusing to engage in a certain relationship (e.g. with an organization or person). Often spans multiple dates (If so, select “more than one” day under Yes/No). When athlete’s refuse to play, it’s often difficult to determine whether the form is ‘strike’ or ‘boycott’ - click [here](#) for more clarification on this issue.
- **Hunger strike** - Often spans multiple dates (If so, select “more than one” day under Yes/No).
- **Information distribution** - Select this if protesters are physically distributing paper/flyers to other people.
- **March** - Protest starts in one location and then travels elsewhere, typically along a planned route. This could include intentional movement that protestors describe as a march or procession. In the article description, make it clear what protestors understand is going on and include a march title if provided. Edge cases that probably are not marches: protestors are required to move from one building to another, protestors are following a target.
- **Occupation/sit-in** - Protesters refuse to leave a location. Could be a camp.

- **Petition** - A formal written request appealing to authority, typically signed by many people, usually spanning multiple dates. May be formatted as a letter. May be electronic, e.g. email, Facebook. Names of participants usually are not recorded, which is fine. A petition is often in conjunction with a protest event involving at least one other protest form; in that case, code it as one event.
- **Picketing** - Standing outside a venue where something significant occurs, often in an effort to persuade the party targeted to meet demands or cease operations (such as impeding others to enter a place) . It is normally related to labour or public policy issues. Often spans multiple dates (If so, select “more than one” day under Yes/No).
- **Press conference by protestors**
- **Property damage** - E.g. a group of students entering the office of the president and destroying computers and files; students painting the walls of a building; defacing or burning a flag; vandalism done by protestors as part of their protest action, as described by protestors or the journalist.
- **Rally/demonstration** - Many people gather in one place, often there is at least one speaker. Rallies and demonstrations often co-occur with or include other events, e.g. marches, symbolic actions. Includes speakers that gather to preach hate. Includes speeches or other ways of addressing people there not captured under other forms like press conference (e.g. reading demands) that take place before/after/during a march.
 - Oftentimes, journalists will use the term ‘demonstration’ as a synonym for ‘protest’. As a result, you should not automatically select this option anytime an article uses the word ‘demonstration’ when describing an event. If an article refers to an event as a ‘demonstration’, but the event lacks any of the characteristics of a rally/demonstration, you should *not* select this option.
- **Riot** - A violent public disturbance of the peace by a crowd. Also usually includes property damage.
- **Strike/walkout/lockout** - Typically, a refusal to provide a service or product. This tends to be for a refusal to work, as in a labor strike, or participate in another activity like attending class, or if the protestors call what they are doing a strike, walkout or lockout. Often spans multiple dates (If so, select “more than one” day under Yes/No). Note: lockouts should only be coded as a protest event when they are initiated by workers, not when they are initiated by employers. When athlete’s refuse to play, it’s often difficult to determine whether the form is ‘strike’ or ‘boycott’ - click [here](#) for more clarification on this issue.
- **Symbolic display/symbolic action** - A symbolic display/action is more than just a slogan. e.g., students stage a die-in or wear gags as the main action or a major action. Another example is athletes or marching band kneeling, sitting, or raising a fist (invoking Black Power Movement) during the national anthem at a sports event and also related actions like

hands on shoulders or linking arms during national anthem (which happened, for example, in the NBA and NFL, due to backlash against kneeling); because of Kaepernick, kneeling has become symbolic because (at least for him) it is meant to signal respect for patriotism (e.g. the troops) but opposition to issues such as campus racism or police violence. Wearing a certain piece of clothing, such as white shirts, is not a symbolic display, unless the protestors make clear that the color white means something for them.

- **Vigil** - Being silent and quietly waiting and/or praying, esp. at night. The vigil must be related to a politicized issue or a person or group who has taken on important symbolic meaning connected to a political issue (e.g. Michael Brown's death). A moment of silence is not considered a vigil.
- **Violence/attack against persons by protestors** - Protestors engage in violence against other people.
- **Other Form** - Includes a variety of actions such as:
 - Teach-in - this depends on context, but typically it is a protest if protestors or the journalist refers to as a protest or if the teach-in that are part of one continuous protest event that involves other actions (ex/ a march, followed by a teach-in).
 - Distribution of t-shirts and bracelets or other non-paper items, and
 - Moments of silence (if this is the only action)
 - Issuing a list of demands if students physically presented demands to administrators or a group/organization sends the demands to the target
 - Virtual protest, e.g. a letter writing campaign, social media campaign, December Dial (#2734), mass sending of emails to a target (e.g. emailing demands to administration) (similar to a December Dial), a Facebook occupation (#10502), social media campaign (#11467). If it is an online-only petition, select "petition," not Other. Only code virtual protest if it concerns a higher ed issue or if students physically gather/act on campus, e.g. 14117.
 - Twitter campaigns/Twitter hashtags that push for social action (these are tricky, and so if you come across an event like this and are unsure of whether to code it or not, bring it to the group for discussion).
 - Students silently holding signs at a university event like a talk (#18053)
 - Tabling alone is rarely a codeable protest form, as the primary goal tends to be informational, but this will depend on the context.
 - Photo campaigns (#4528) when there is a physical gathering, not just posted on social media.

Again, if you do not know the form of the event, then you do not select any option.

Issue vs. Racial Issue

A codeable protest must have a form or issue. **In MPEDS, there are two different types of issues: general (non-racial) and racial.** If you do not know the issue of the event, then you **do not** select any option. These are not mutually exclusive lists. Sometimes you might find both general issues and racial issues in an article.

If the protest concerns an issue listed under Racial Issues but, in the article, it is not connected to race, and there is no appropriate alternative option listed under General Issues, then select “Other issue” in the Issues preset list.

If the issue is “police violence/anti-law enforcement” and the article does not mention or imply that it’s a racial problem, only select this option under Issues. If the article presents “police violence/anti-law enforcement” as a racial issue (with or without a mention of other problems with law enforcement), select this option under Racial Issues. Whenever possible, use the protestors’ understanding of the issue.

About the interface: If you can’t see the entire list, zoom out to make the screen smaller.

Issues

This a list of general, non-racial issues. For an example, [click here](#).

- **Abortion Access (For)/Pro-choice**
- **Abortion (Against)/Pro-life**
- **Accessibility**
- **Animal rights**
- **Anti-colonialism/political independence** - Includes calls for sovereignty and freedom from imperialist/colonial policies.
- **Anti-war/peace** - E.g. opposition to militarization or military spending, Often selected for Palestinian liberation.
- **Domestic foreign policy** - Laws and policies of the U.S. government (for U.S. protests) or Canadian government (for Canadian protests) involving international issues (not typically immigration into the relevant country).
- **Economy/inequality** - Makes a connection between economic issues (e.g., wages, cost of housing) to broader unfairness in the economy. Often, protestors are advocating for a higher

minimum wage/calls for a livable or living wage. Also includes: austerity measures, the role that universities have in urban development and gentrification.

- **Environmental**
- **Faith-based discrimination** - Mistreatment of someone or a group based on their religion, or because they are atheists. Select this if protestors are opposing faith-based discrimination, e.g. a Jewish student organization protesting anti-semitism. Always select this option when protestors are opposed to Islamophobia or anti-Semitism. If the protesters express anti-Semitic and/or Islamophobic views, also select Far Right/Alt Right (For); this includes preachers preaching hate against group(s) because their religion or their lack thereof. Note that in cases of Islamophobia or anti-Semitism, the discrimination may have a racial or ethnic component also, or even be viewed solely as a racial issue. However, you should still select this option in those cases. You can select corresponding Racial Issues along with this category, however, unless the racial discrimination is explicitly mentioned in the article, you should only code as faith-based.
- **Far Right/Alt Right (Against)** - Select if protestors oppose Milo Y, Ben Shapiro, Charles Murray, Gavin McGinnis, Ann Coulter, or similar figures as well as far right/alt right organizations - even if the speakers or their supporters do not explicitly identify this way. *e.g. "anti-fascist."*
- **Far Right/Alt Right (For)** - Select if protestors support Milo Y, Ben Shapiro, Charles Murray, Gavin McGinnis, Ann Coulter, or similar figures as well as far right/alt right organizations - even if the speakers or their supporters do not explicitly identify this way. *If the protesters express anti-Semitic and/or Islamophobic views, also select Faith-based discrimination.*
- **Feminism/women's issues**
- **Free speech** - When protestors are calling for "free speech," "freedom of speech," "freedom of expression," often phrased as "First Amendment" in the U.S. Note that this term is highly politicized, so protestors who are critical of free speech politics may not use that term, but still select "free speech" if that is what protestors are reacting to.
- **Gun control**
- **Gun owner rights**
- **Hate crimes/anti-minority violence**
- **Hate speech** - words/forms of communication with the intent to incite violence or harm and/or what protestors identify as non-racial discriminatory/prejudicial speech. Includes slurs and hateful speech or comments described by protestors in language such as "hate speech" or "hateful." This could be on social media. Could often be selected along with campus climate.

- Human rights - use this code for references to or claims about (usually international) human rights law, e.g. Palestinian human rights, violation of Armenian human rights. Do not use it for workplace rights in Canada (select “Other issue”). If it is a human rights issue and also a racial issue, check this option and also check at least one option in the Racial Issues list. Do not select this automatically just because there is a racial issue.
- **LGB+/Sexual orientation (Against)**
- **LGB+/Sexual orientation (For)**
- **Labour and work** -Includes advocating for a higher minimum wage/calls for a livable wage.
- **Men’s rights** - Advocates for men’s causes, often with a sexist and/or anti-feminist position.
- **Political corruption/malfeasance** - In government. Political corruption is the use of power by government officials in their official duties to violate rules, done for illegitimate personal enrichment, e.g. bribery, extortion, cronyism, and embezzlement. Malfeasance is broader: intentional conduct that is wrongful or unlawful by government officials or public employees, including misuse of government power to repress political opponents. This can be complicated in the Trump years because Trump supporters use the idea of corruption inaccurately, but continue to rely on the protestors’ perspective/language to identify the issue.
- **Pro-Israel/Zionism**
- **Pro-Palestine/BDS** - Also select ‘Human rights’ or ‘Anti-war/Peace’ if the protestors use these terms or frame the protest issue in this way. Protestors may use related language such as anti-Israeli apartheid.
- **Police violence/anti-law enforcement/criminal justice** - Select only if there’s no racial issue mentioned or implied by the protestors, e.g. when domestic police are militarized, over aggression toward protestors, campus security is accused of being abusive. Select for non-racial issues involving prisons, such as use of prison labour for campus jobs. If the issue involves campus security, also select University Governance. If a racial issue is acknowledged in the article, then select “police violence” under the Racial Issues list. If it is a combination of racial and non-racial issues with the police, only select it under the racial list.
- **Pro-law enforcement** - Events in support of police or any law enforcement agents or agencies.
- **Public funding for higher education** - When protestors are focused on the state/province/federal government.
- **Sexual assault/violence**

- **Social services and welfare** - As provided (or not) by the government, not the university. Includes public transit.
- **Traditional marriage/family** - Advocates that legal marriage/parenting (e.g. adoption) should only be accessible to couples comprised of a heterosexual man and a heterosexual woman who conform to normative (cis) gender identities; often argued on the grounds of religion (esp. Christianity).
- **Transgender issues (Against)** - Includes gender identity (e.g. non-binary). e.g. support for discriminatory North Carolina bathroom bill.
- **Transgender issues (For)** - Includes gender identity (e.g. non-binary). e.g. opposition to discriminatory North Carolina bathroom bill.
- **Trump and/or his administration (Against)** - Select this option if protestors explicitly refer to Trump or make an understood reference (e.g. the President, the administration, the Orange Man, etc). Anti-Trump protests often raise many issues, some of which can be very vague (e.g. diversity) and the coding would get very inefficient if we select them all. For this reason, anti-Trump protests typically should be coded as only this category and not additional issues. Additional issues should be coded if:
 - There are other **headline issues**, such as immigration. For Muslim Ban, select both immigration and faith-based discrimination.
 - Protestors are protesting against Trump for being a **racist**, or are solely protesting against him for being a racist. Select the relevant Racial Issues.
 - There is **another target** for an issue, such as demanding the university become a sanctuary campus (issue: university governance), code that issue, too

This should also be reflected in text select (i.e. do not text select every single issue protestors raise). Some of these additional issues may get included in the event description.
- **Trump and/or his administration (For)**
- **Tuition, fees, financial aid** - Typically, protestors are focused on the university. Also includes student debt.
- **University governance, admin, policies, programs, curriculum** - An issue related to how leaders make decisions and the process of decision-making. The process of decision-making might include faculty, administrators and students. It might be related to how money is allocated, such as investment or divestment, or to hiring policies and support services offered.
- **Not relevant** - Select if it is a racial issue.

- **Other Issue** - This includes:
 - Corporate practices
 - Access to higher education
 - Science if there is no environmental issue.
 - Armenian genocide

If you do not know the issue of the event, then you do not select any option.

Racial Issues

For Racial Issues, we are interested in more detailed information, listed below. If the event does not raise a racial issue, click “Not relevant” in this section. For an example, [click here](#).

- **Affirmative action (Against)**
- **Affirmative action (For)**
- **All Lives Matter/Anti-BLM** - These reactionary, counterprotest slogans or arguments typically are used to discredit Black Lives Matter. Select this if the protesters identify themselves as “All Lives Matter.” May also be pro-police. All Lives Matter was likely more common prior to summer 2016; once Trump came into office, Anti-BLM likely became more common.
- **Anti-racism** - Only select if the protestors mention the word racism, racist, racial injustice, bigotry, discrimination, or if they mention/make reference to mistreatment experienced by named racial/ethnic groups (ex/ Hispanic, South Asian, etc.). Anti-racist issues identify the existence of power imbalances between marginalized racialized groups/people of color and dominant racial groups/white people.
- **Campus climate** - How people of color feel about their experiences of attending classes, living, spending time, and/or working at the university, esp others’ attitudes and behaviors toward them (e.g. disrespectful, references to microaggressions, “we don’t feel safe here”), as people of color.
- **Cultural appropriation** - e.g., Native American mascots.
- **Hate crimes/Anti-minority violence** - Racially motivated crime.
- **Hate speech** - Words/forms of communication with the intent to incite violence or harm and/or what protestors identify as racist/prejudicial speech. Includes racial slurs and racist

speech or comments described by protestors in language such as “hate speech” or “hateful.” This could be on social media. Often selected along with campus climate.

- **Indigenous issues** - Typically includes sovereignty, governance, and reconciliation issues. Also includes the genocide against indigenous peoples.
- **Immigration (Against)**
- **Immigration (For)**
- **Memorials & anniversaries** - Often references to civil rights protest events and often not the only issue
- **Police violence** - includes race-related police behavior that protestors consider unacceptable, such as arresting someone.
- **Prison/mass incarceration**
- **Pro-police** - May also be All Lives Matter.
- **Racial/ethnic pride - minority**
- **Racial/ethnic pride - white**
- **Racist/racialized symbols** - E.g. opposition to or defense of Confederate statues, a KKK robe, the name of a building if students describe it as racist. Include graffiti, e.g., the Nazi symbol, if that is a focus of the protest.
- **Reparations** - Typically pertains to African American issues.
- **University governance, admin, policies, programs, curriculum** - A racialized issue related to how leaders make decisions and the process of decision-making. The process of decision-making might include faculty, administrators and students. It might be related to underrepresentation in hiring and support services offered.
- **White supremacy (Against)**
- **White supremacy (For)** - Explicit pro-white claims, typically made by off-campus groups, e.g, Richard Spencer. May be overtly racist, anti-semitic, and/or Islamophobic.
- **Not relevant** - select if it is a General Issue.
- **Other Issue** - e.g., racial issues with use of social media, genocide with a racial component. If the genocide has a racial component and other components (such as faith, sexual orientation, etc.) you should still only select this option.

If you do not know the issue of the event, then you do not select any option.

Target

A target is **one or more individuals and/or one or more organizations that the protestors identify as who/what they oppose or are protesting against**. See above (under Text Select tab) for more details. For an example, [click here](#).

- **Domestic government** - Includes government at the local, state, and national level as well as juries in court trials. Also includes a government official if the government official is the ultimate decision maker of a government policy using the power granted by the office (e.g. Trump taking executive action in pardoning Arpaio, the “Muslim Ban”) or other government-related issue (e.g. rule making). Look out for named entities or general bodies that are asked to do something, e.g. Oakland City Council, the grand jury, legislators. If protestors target Trump prior to his election win, or when he was president-elect, the target is ‘Individual.’ If protestors target Trump when he was president, at least one target is ‘Domestic Government’ - the target may also be ‘Individual’ in these cases if protestors are also targeting Trump for actions he took prior to being a politician.
- **Ethnic/racial group**
- **Foreign government**
- **Individual** - If the protestors approach or name the president of a university as the ultimate decision maker of a university policy or other university-related issue (e.g. occupy their office because they are a figurehead for the university), then at least one target is the university. If the protestors approach or name a government official, and the government official is the ultimate decision maker of a government policy using the power granted by the office, then at least one target is Domestic government. However, if the protest is about the individual’s past actions prior to their official role as a university/government official, calls for their resignation, calls for their apology, or calls for individual actions apart from their official duties (ex/ release of their birth certificate), then at least one target is the individual. If protestors target Trump prior to his election win, or when he was president-elect, the target is ‘Individual.’ If protestors target Trump when he was president, at least one target is ‘Domestic Government’ - the target may also be ‘Individual’ in these cases if protestors are also targeting Trump for actions he took prior to being a politician.
- **Intergovernmental organization** - e.g. the United Nations.
- **Medical facility/organization** - If the target of the protest is Planned Parenthood, select this option and “non-governmental organization.”
- **Non-governmental organization** - Not-for-profit organizations. If the target of the protest is Planned Parenthood, select this option and “Medical facility/organization.”

- **Other minority group** - A group not defined by its race/ethnicity.
- **Police** - Select when the protest issue is related to police violence, racism in policing, corruption in policing, etc. If the target is campus police, also select University/school.
- **Political party** - A political party that is **not** currently in power. If the protest is targeting the political party that is in power, select “domestic government.”
- **Private/business**
- **University/school** - E.g. If the president of a university is the ultimate decision maker of a university policy or other university-related issue, then the target is the university. However, if the protest is about the individual’s current or past actions or position specifically, then the target is individual. For example, asking for someone’s resignation versus just occupying their office because of some administrative decision or issue.
- **Other target** - Unspecified event or person, a particular event, or people at an event. It also includes student clubs or organizations and religious institutions such as churches.
- **No target** - When protesters have no identified individual or group that they oppose, such as a protest to show solidarity with some other group or person.

For counter-protests:

In a reactionary protest aiming to show a different position than another protest (e.g. a pro-police event at the same time as a Black Lives Matter event), there is often no target, i.e. counter-protesters do not identify anyone as their opposition, not even the original protest. In this case, select “No target.” However, if the counter-protest is in opposition to the original protest and/or action (e.g., a protest objecting to another group’s decision to invite a controversial speaker), then the counter-protesters usually have a target (e.g., the original protest group, an invited speaker). In this case, choose the appropriate target.

When you have finished answering all the questions on all the tabs (yay!), select “Mark Done and Go to Next.”

Record the number(s) of the article(s) you have coded in your timesheet.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR UNIQUE PROTESTS

2012 Quebec Student Strike Protests

Introduction

In this section, you can find coding information specific to the 2012 Quebec student strike protests against the provincial government's tuition hikes. Articles related to this series of protest events raised new methodological and coding questions. This is due to:

- 1) The large scale of events taking place simultaneously at different universities throughout Quebec,
- 2) The complicated federated structure of student unions in Canada, which function similar to labour unions, and which allowed different faculty unions within a single university to differ in the start and end date of their strikes, the length of their strikes, and other protest forms included in their strike actions (picketing, blockade, etc),
- 3) And the nature of news coverage of the events, which often assumed that readers already had a baseline knowledge of the strikes taking place (such as the target of the protests), and often did not include information that was significant for coding purposes related to this project (such as the start date of strike actions).

The following coding procedures were developed in order to account for the unique nature of the media coverage surrounding the Quebec student strikes, and apply only to articles relating to the Quebec student strikes.

Coding the Quebec Student Strikes

For the Quebec student strikes, the unions participating in the strikes were part of a complicated federated structure. Some unions started and/or ended their strike actions on different dates. Use the following coding procedures when coding the Quebec student strikes:

- 1) If an article only refers to the Quebec student strikes generally, with no mention of separate student unions, then you should code a single event for the general strike (If an article reports on the Quebec student strikes generally, and does not provide or suggest a start date for the strikes, mention this in the article description and code the strike start date as 2012-02-13),
- 2) If the article mentions separate unions on strike, then you should code a separate event for each union mentioned,

- 3) If an article mentions strikes held by unions, and also mentions the general strike, you should create a separate entry for each of the units mentioned, and also create an entry for the general strike.

If an article only reports on one of the unions on strike, note in the article description that you know there were multiple unions on strike, but the article only mentions one of the unions.

Student Strike Spreadsheets

The vast majority of articles reporting on strikes taking place at schools in Quebec will not provide a start date for strike actions. In these cases, you should obtain this information from the spreadsheets linked below, which contain the start dates for strikes held by faculty associations participating in strikes at each respective school.

For the Concordia Student Strike Spreadsheet, [click here](#).⁸

For the McGill Student Strike Spreadsheet, [click here](#).⁹

If you come across an article reporting on a strike that is not covered in these spreadsheets, select the approximate start date for the event, and enter the start date as the earliest start date contained in the spreadsheet.

If an article reports on the Quebec student strikes generally, and does not provide or suggest a start date for the strikes, mention this in the article description and code the strike start date as 2012-02-13.

Standardized Options & Presets

Part of a larger higher education campaign:

Many articles will not mention the explicit coordination between identifiable on-campus groups that took place during the Quebec student strikes. You should still select **“part of a larger campaign within a university or across universities”** under **“Does this event”** in these cases. Mention in the article description that the article does not mention this explicitly, but that you know this from other Quebec student strike articles.

⁸ Internal document. Contained data for: Organization/Union Name , Start Date, End Date, Form (other than strike), Target (other than provincial government), Articles Used for Start Date, Articles Used for Form, Articles Used for Target, Notes.

⁹ Internal document. Contained data for: Organization/Union Name , Start Date, End Date, Form (other than strike), Target (other than provincial government), Articles Used for Start Date, Articles Used for Form, Articles Used for Target, Notes.

Target:

Many articles will not mention that the target of the protests is the provincial government. You should still select “**domestic government**” under the “**target**” preset. Note in the article description that the article does not mention this explicitly, but that you know this from other Quebec student strike articles.

Selecting Forms

Picketing & Blockade/slowdown/disruption:

Many articles will report on students picketing, blocking others from entering classrooms, or both picketing and blocking. When coding these articles, you should select any and all forms related to picketing/blocking as mentioned in the article.

For example, if the article only mentions that students picketed, select only **picketing** as the form. If the article mentions that students picketed, and mentions that students blocked others from entering classrooms, select both **picketing** and **blockade/slowdown/disruption** as the forms.

Quebec Student Strike vs. Quebec Student Boycott:

The language that participants use to describe the student protests is politicized and contentious. Student protestors tend to describe their protest as a “strike.” However, some journalists, some students, many administrators, and many government officials who oppose the protests will occasionally or exclusively refer to the protests as a “boycott.” You should **not** select **boycott** as the form for any of these events, even if the article only uses the word ‘boycott.’ You should **only** select **strike** and any other forms included in the article’s description of the event (such as a picket).

Using Information from Other Articles

Some articles will report on students participating in the strike as using other protest forms (ex. picketing). Some articles will also mention that striking students have identified protest targets other than the provincial government (ex. an individual who supports the tuition hikes). However, other articles reporting on the same event will often not mention these secondary protest forms and targets. You should not use the information from articles that report on secondary protest forms/targets to inform your coding of other articles reporting on the same strike.

For example, if an article mentions that striking students from the Fine Arts Association also picketed, and a later article reporting on the Fine Arts Association strike does not mention that students had picketed, you should not use the information from the earlier article to select picketing

as a form for the later article. The rationale is that we do not expect you to retain, muchless retrieve, that level of detailed knowledge from other articles.

However, you should enter this information into the corresponding Student Strike Spreadsheet under the categories of **“Form (other than strike)”** or **“Target (other than provincial government),”** and cite the article number.

2015 York/UofT Strike Protests

Introduction

In this section, you can find coding information specific to the York/UofT strikes that were held by faculty against their respective administrations due to a breakdown in contract negotiations. Articles related to this series of protest events raised new methodological and coding questions. This is due to:

- 1) the large scale of events taking place simultaneously over an extended period of time and, in the case of UofT, at different campuses,
- 2) the complicated structure of the labour unions that were involved, which allowed different units within unions to differ in the start and end date of their strikes, the length of their strikes, secondary protest issues, and other protest forms included in their strike actions (picketing, blockade, etc),
- 3) and the nature of news coverage of the events, which often assumed that readers already had a baseline knowledge of the strikes taking place (such as the target of the protests), and often did not include information that was significant for coding purposes related to this project (such as the start date of strike actions).

The following coding procedures were developed in order to account for the unique nature of the media coverage surrounding the York/UofT strikes, and apply **only** to articles relating to the York/UofT strikes.

Coding the York/UofT Strikes

For the UofT/York strikes, the unions participating in the strikes were composed of multiple units, some of which started and/or ended their strike actions on different dates. Use the following coding procedures when coding the York/UofT strikes:

- 1) If the article mentions separate units on strike, then you should code a separate event for each unit mentioned,

- 2) **This point only applies to York:** If an article only refers to the union's strike generally, with no mention of separate units, then you should code that general strike as one event,
 - a) Instructions for how to code these types of events at UofT are located in the next section, 'Coding the strikes at UofT.'

- 3) **This point only applies to York:** If an article mentions strikes held by units, and also mentions the general strike, you should create a separate entry for each of the units mentioned, and also create an entry for the general strike.
 - a) This point doesn't apply to UofT because although unions at York and UofT are complicated because of their organization, this is further complicated at UofT due to its tri-campus system.

If an article only reports on one of the units on strike, note in the article description that you know there were multiple units on strike, but the article only mentions one of the units.

When coding UofT/York Strikes, under 'Text Select - Movement organizations,' you should always select the Union name (eg: CUPE 3903) under movement organizations, as well as the Unit name (eg: Unit 3) for each respective event.

Coding the Strikes at UofT

For the strikes at UofT, the events are more complicated because UofT has three campuses. The following are additional coding procedures that apply only to the UofT strikes:

- 1) If an article only refers to the strikes generally across the three campuses, select '**Does this event - Occur in multiple cities,**' and code the strike as one event. In the location tab, enter 'Toronto, ON, Canada,' as St. George is the flagship campus for the University of Toronto.

Example: Members of CUPE 3902 Unit 1 at the University of Toronto went on strike.

- 2) If the article mentions strikes at specific campuses, then you should code a separate event for each campus mentioned.

- 3) If the article mentions solidarity or protests related to the strikes that happened generally across the three campuses, select '**Does this event - Occur in multiple cities,**' and code the protest as one event. In the location tab, enter 'Toronto, ON, Canada,' as St. George is the flagship campus for the University of Toronto.

Example: UofT undergraduate students participated in a UofT-Wide Walkout in solidarity with CUPE Local 3902 Unit 1.

- 4) If the article mentions solidarity or protests related to the strikes that happened at specific campuses, code separate events for each campus mentioned.

Text Select Categories

Related protests involving other universities:

Relationship between strike action(s) and solidarity events

When coding strike actions, whether the strike action is mentioned generally across the three campuses or at specific UofT campuses, solidarity events should be captured under this category for all codeable strike actions. In these cases, solidarity events should be captured under this category regardless of which of the three UofT campuses the solidarity event took place.

Example #1: An article mentions a general strike across the three UofT campuses, and undergraduate students holding solidarity rallies at UTM and UTSG. Under the coding for the general strike, both of the solidarity rallies should be captured under this category.

Example #2: An article mentions strike actions being held at UTSG and UTM, and solidarity walkouts being held by undergraduate students at UTM and UTSG. Under the separate codings for both of the strike actions at UTSG and UTM, the solidarity events should be captured under this category.

Relationship between strike action(s)

When coding strike actions at specific campuses, the relationship between the events should get captured under this category if the article indicates (implicitly or explicitly) that there was either *inspiration* or *coordination* between the events.

Example: An article mentions that CUPE 3902 members at UTSG planned a walkout, and that they coordinated with CUPE 3902 members at UTM to also participate in the walkout. Under the codings for these events, the inspiration/coordination should be captured under this category.

Relationship between solidarity events

When coding solidarity events at specific campuses, the relationship between the events should get captured under this category if the article indicates (implicitly or explicitly) that there was either *inspiration* or *coordination* between the events.

Example: An article mentions that students at UTM held a sit-in in coordination with students that held a walk-out at UTSC in solidarity with members of CUPE 3902 on strike. Under the codings for these solidarity events, the inspiration/coordination between the solidarity should be captured under this category.

Other university where protest occurs:

Since the location of the university (and therefore the campus) is mentioned in the Basic Info geolocation box, this text select category is redundant. Do not select this category.

York/UofT Strikes Spreadsheets

Many of the articles reporting on the York/UofT strikes will not provide a start date for strike actions. In these cases, you should obtain this information from the spreadsheet linked below, which contains the start dates for strikes held by faculty associations participating in strikes at each respective school.

For the York/UofT Strikes Spreadsheet, [*click here*](#).¹⁰

Standardized Options & Presets

Part of a larger higher education on-campus campaign:

Many articles will not mention the explicit coordination between identifiable units that took place during the UofT/York strikes. You should still select **“part of a larger campaign within a university or across universities”** under **“Does this event”** in these cases. Mention in the article description that the article does not mention this explicitly, but that you know this from other UofT/York strike articles.

Target:

Sometimes articles reporting on the UofT/York strikes won't mention a target. You should always select **“University/school”** under the **“Target”** preset. Note in the article description that the article does not mention this explicitly, but that you know this from other UofT/York strike articles.

¹⁰ Internal document. Contained data for: Organization/Union Name , Start Date, End Date, Form (other than strike), Target (other than provincial government), Articles Used for Start Date, Articles Used for Form, Articles Used for Target, Notes.

Selecting Forms

Picketing & Blockade/slowdown/disruption:

Many articles will report on protestors picketing, blocking others from entering campus buildings, or both picketing and blocking. When coding these articles, you should select any and all forms related to picketing/blocking as mentioned in the article.

For example, if the article only mentions that protestors picketed, select only **picketing** as the form. If the article mentions that protestors picketed, and mentions that protestors blocked others from entering a building, select both **picketing** and **blockade/slowdown/disruption** as the forms.

Selecting Issues

For articles reporting on the York/UofT strikes, you should always select the Preset Issues as both **labor and work** and **University governance, admin, policies, programs, curriculum**. If the protestors raise any other issues as part of their protest, select those issues in addition to these.

Using Information from Other Articles

Some articles will report on protestors participating in the strike as using other protest forms (ex. picketing). Some articles will also mention that protestors on strike have identified protest targets other than their respective university (ex. an individual who has spoken out against the unions). However, other articles reporting on the same event will often not mention these secondary protest forms and targets. You should **not** use the information from articles that report on secondary protest forms/targets to inform your coding of other articles reporting on the same strike.

For example, if an article mentions that protestors on strike at CUPE 3902 also picketed, and a later article reporting on the CUPE 3902 strike does not mention that protestors had picketed, you should **not** use the information from the earlier article to select picketing as a form for the later article. The rationale is that we do not expect you to retain, muchless retrieve, that level of detailed knowledge from other articles.

However, you should enter this information into the York/UofT Strikes Spreadsheet under the categories of **“Form (other than strike)”** or **“Target (other than provincial government),”** and cite the article number.

Appendix: Coding Examples

In this section, you can find examples of coding for some of the components found in the interface. These examples will guide your coding, so when in doubt, check them out. If you have any questions, write them down in the coders question spreadsheet and bring them up during team meetings.

Tab 1: Basic info

Description for disqualified article:

Article #12170 - Montreal Solidarity for Aleppo and Anger for Putin	
Good	Not so good
<p>Provides a very brief summary of the article and then clearly identifies why the article is not codeable.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Article reports on protestors gathering near the Russian consulate in Montreal to march in solidarity for Aleppo's citizens and to protest Russian-led forces bombing the city. The event was off-campus and unrelated to higher education.</p>	<p>Does not clearly identify why the article is not codeable. It mentions that the event is off-campus, but does not establish that the event is unrelated to higher education. The summary of the article could also include a bit more detail.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>The article reports on protestors marching off-campus due to the situation in Aleppo. The event is not codeable.</p>

***** Also make sure to select the corresponding disqualifying option(s) under the 'Yes/No' tab**

Description of article:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Provided the broader issue that the article discusses, as well as the location and the issues.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Report on the approval by a committee to send a plan to increase tuition by up to 5 percent to the University of California's board of regents. Protesters were present at the meeting disapproving of the tuition plan. (2555)</p>	<p>Needed more description about article:</p> <p>Students at UCLA protesting higher tuition costs (2573)</p>
Article #11434 - #BlackLivesMatter: Montreal stands with Ferguson	
Good	Not so good
<p>Brief but includes location, actors, type of protest and issue:</p> <p>This article is about a vigil at McGill University in solidarity with ongoing demonstrations in Ferguson, Missouri, and to mourn Michael Brown and other victims of police violence against racialized communities. The event followed the November 24 announcement of a grand jury's decision not to indict police officer Darren Wilson for the fatal shooting of Brown. One speaker at the vigil related protest issues to the role of university students. Related rallies took place in many other Canadian cities, with around 2,000 participating in Toronto and hundreds in Ottawa and Calgary, but it's unclear whether these were on campuses or not. (19061)</p>	<p>Too much descriptive information. Includes information that should be in the event description (red text):</p> <p>This article describes a vigil, organized by the McGill Black Students' Network (BSN), where members of the McGill community gathered to express their solidarity with the ongoing demonstrations in Ferguson, Missouri, and to mourn Michael Brown and other victims of police violence against racialized communities. The event followed the announcement of a grand jury's decision not to indict police officer Darren Wilson for the fatal shooting of Brown, an unarmed black teenager, in August. Solidarity rallies took place in many other Canadian cities, with around 2,000</p>

	<p>participating in Toronto and hundreds in Ottawa and Calgary. Students, community members and other campus organizations listened to emotional speeches and poetry, sang a song and took part in a four minute moment of silence. Many attendees acknowledged the fear of being a racial minority in North America and shared their stories and feelings.</p>
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Description of article when using information from a previous article to inform coding:

Article #4985 - Labor complaints have been filed against CSU for bargaining in 'bad faith'	
Good	Not so good
<p>Cited the past article being used to inform coding and identified the specific information being used from that article.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>Article reports on members of the California Faculty Association rallying outside of the California State University Chancellor's Office, along with supporters, accusing CSU for wrongdoing during labour bargaining processes. The article does not explicitly mention whether students were involved in the event, however, article #4742 makes it clear that students participated in the event.</p>	<p>Did not cite the previous article being used to inform coding.</p> <p>Example:</p> <p>The article reports on a rally outside of the Chancellor's Office in Long Beach in which CSU faculty and supporters protested against CSU for their unfair actions during the bargaining process. The article doesn't mention whether students participated, but I know from previous articles that students were present at the event.</p>

Description of event:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Provided information about the actors, their actions and the issues they are targeting:</p> <p>Example 1:</p> <p>The event started with more than 100 students blockading the building in which the meeting was held at the University of California San Francisco. Additionally, more than 300 UC students attended the meeting itself in protest, during which time at least one student was arrested and a glass door was broken. The students were protesting in order to express their anger at the increase in tuition. (2709)</p> <p>Example 2:</p> <p>Students blocked the entrance of the meeting place and attended the meeting in protest. Some protests destroyed property and scuffled with police. (2534)</p>	<p>Needed capital letters and full sentences. Avoid typos:</p> <p>students rallied outside the meeting and protested the plan - 100 students came to block entrances to the meeting place, chanting slogans - 300 in total (2546)</p> <p>Missing how many people participated and what they were doing (include if available):</p> <p>Students at UCLA rallied to protest tuition increases at a UC Board of Regents meeting. (2573)</p>
Article #235 - Badgers Against Racism rally protests 'Cinco de Mifflin' theme	
Good	Not so good
Includes location inside the university, who	Forgets to name the movement

<p>is protesting (including organization), and the issue:</p> <p>A crowd of students, faculty and community members rallied at East Campus Mall Friday afternoon to support Badgers Against Racism's efforts against the use of the term "Cinco de Mifflin" in connection with the Mifflin Street Block Party. (2761)</p>	<p>organization:</p> <p>The event was held at East Campus Mall to bring awareness to the historical importance of Cinco de Mayo and the subsequent disregard that attendees held for the importance of the date. The coalition condemned it as an appropriation of culture. (2924)</p>
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Start date, End date, and Location:

Start date

End date

Location (City, State/Province, Country)

Tab 2: Yes/No

Basic Info	Yes/No	Text Select	Preset
Is the start date exact or approximate?			
<input checked="" type="radio"/> Exact			
<input type="radio"/> Approximate			
Does this event span one day or more than one day?			
<input checked="" type="radio"/> One			
<input type="radio"/> More than one			
Disqualifying information			
<input type="checkbox"/> no student protest event			
<input type="checkbox"/> off-campus with no higher ed issue			
<input type="checkbox"/> outside of Canada or the US			
<input type="checkbox"/> editorial/opinion			
<input type="checkbox"/> editorial/opinion with protest information			
<input type="checkbox"/> historical (> 1 year) event or outside date range			
<input type="checkbox"/> overly vague			
<input type="checkbox"/> duplicate article			
Does this event			
<input type="checkbox"/> off-campus with a higher ed issue			
<input type="checkbox"/> contain slogans or other protest symbols			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> contain direct quotes			
<input type="checkbox"/> part of a larger on-campus campaign			
<input type="checkbox"/> ritualized or cyclical			
<input type="checkbox"/> a counter-protest			
Does this article			
<input type="checkbox"/> have an inaccurate date			

Don't forget to select.

Select if article or event cannot be coded.

If article is codable, then check if applicable.

If issues with date, then select.

Tab 3: Text select

Text select format:

Article #3928 - Students protest at Hillary Clinton campaign event	
Good	Not so good
<p>Individual and unrelated issues are text selected separately in discrete chunks:</p> <p>“Clinton's stance on fracking (11436)”</p> <p>“her relationship with corporations (11436)”</p> <p>“what she would do for the transgender community (11436)”</p> <p>“the Black Lives Matter movement. (11436)”</p>	<p>The protestors’ diverse range of issues are text selected together in a long sentence:</p> <p>“Clinton's stance on fracking, her relationship with corporations and what she would do for the transgender community and the Black Lives Matter movement. (13307)”</p>

Actors:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Includes all actors with names and titles, when appropriate:</p> <p>Actors ^ +</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">graduate student Maria Zubel. ✕University faculty members ✕students ✕Denise Welte ✕	

Click [here](#) to go back to section.

Actors: Using the Person's Freeform

<p>Article #3006 - Graduated Ohio University activists carry their protesting pasts into new jobs</p>	
<p>Good</p>	<p>Not so good</p>
<p>Used the person's freeform for non-contiguous title and name of individual.</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 10px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p>Persons Freeform</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #add8e6; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;"> <p>Megan Marzec / Former OU Student Senate President</p> </div> <p style="text-align: right; margin-top: 5px;">Save</p> </div>	<p>Selected minimum information instead of using the person's freeform</p> <p>Highlight text and click + for the relevant category.</p> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <p style="text-align: right;">Actions/forms ^ +</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: right;">Actors ^ +</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: right;">Megan Marzec x</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Government officials ^ +</p> <hr/> <p style="text-align: right;">Issues ^ +</p> </div>

Actions/Forms:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Phrases were shorter, each action was selected separately and corresponded with a category in the preset:</p> <p>Highlight text and click + for the relevant category.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Actions/forms ^ +</p> <p style="text-align: right;">rallied ✕</p> <p style="text-align: right;">blockade ✕</p>	<p>Phrases were too long, but the information is relevant:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;"> <p>students rallied outside its meeting (2709)</p> </div> <p>protested the plan (2709)</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;"> <p>at least one student was arrested after a struggle between students and police, in which a glass door was broken in the rear of the building, university police said. A UC Berkeley student was arrested on charges of felony vandalism and inciting a riot, police added. (2709)</p> </div>
Article #235 - Badgers Against Racism rally protests 'Cinco de Mifflin' theme	
Good	Not so good
<p>Only action was selected:</p> <p>Rallied at East Campus Mall (2748)</p>	<p>Provided too much information:</p> <p>A crowd of students, faculty and community members rallied at East Campus Mall Friday afternoon to support Badgers Against Racism's efforts against the use of the term "Cinco de Mifflin" in connection with the Mifflin Street Block Party (2727)</p>

Government officials:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
Included name and title: Governmental officials	Included other information that isn't useful: Gov. Jerry Brown had for the UC, which has given the University steady funding increases in exchange for a tuition freeze (2546)

Issues:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Brief issues and enough information:</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Issues ^ +</p> <p style="text-align: right;">tuition hikes ✕</p> <p style="text-align: right;">increase tuition ✕</p>	<p>Provided too much detail:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;"> <p>increase tuition (2709)</p> <p>a plan to increase tuition by up to 5 percent annually for the next five years depending on state funding (2709)</p> <p>A large majority of the speakers during the public comment portion of the meeting spoke out against the tuition hikes, including UCLA student leaders. (2709)</p> </div>
Article #235 - Badgers Against Racism rally protests 'Cinco de Mifflin' theme	
Good	Not so good
<p>Recorded short sentences:</p> <p>use of the term "Cinco de Mifflin" (2761)</p> <p>Appropriating culture (2761)</p> <p>makes me feel uncomfortable and almost unwelcome because of my culture (2761)</p> <p>stereotypical thinking that can lead to serious</p>	<p>Provided too much information:</p> <p>Students gathered on East Campus Mall to encourage the UW community to be cognizant of racial stereotypes, including 'Cinco de Mifflin' (2727)</p> <p>The formation of the group was a response to the widespread use of the term, "Cinco de Mifflin," according to a statement from the group. (2727)</p>

<p>hate crimes (2761)</p> <p>response to the widespread use of the term, "Cinco de Mifflin," (2748)</p> <p>improving inclusion of all cultures throughout the campus (2748)</p>	<p>promotes stereotypical thinking that can lead to serious hate crimes and is offensive not only to the Mexican-American community, but to people who care about diversity and cultural issues as well. (2727)</p> <p>the alleged hate crime at Delta Upsilon fraternity, are not isolated incidents of racism and are unacceptable. (2727)</p> <p>anizati</p> <p>racial problem. The costumes, the sombreros and the shirts that replace the serpent on the Mexican flag with a beer bong are equally as offensive, (2727)</p>
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Movement organizations:

Article #235 - Badgers Against Racism rally protests 'Cinco de Mifflin' theme	
Good	Not so good
<p>Selected just the names of the organization: Badgers Against Racism (2748)</p>	<p>Selected the target as a movement organization:</p>
Article # 1021 - Detroit students rally on campus against Proposition 2	
Good	Not so good
<p>Selected just the names of the organizations: By Any Means Necessary (6218) the Coalition to Defend Affirmative Action (6218) Integration and Immigrant Rights (6218) Fight for Equality (6218)</p>	<p>Forgot to include the names of other organizations that participated in the event: By Any Means Necessary (6218)</p>

Police actions:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Police actions briefly state what police did and what contact they had with protesters:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p style="text-align: center;">Police actions ^ +</p> <p style="text-align: center;">one student was arrested ✕</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Berkeley student was ... and inciting a riot ✕</p> </div> <p>Full description of action was cut off by interface (this is how it would look like when you code it too). However, full action should say: “Berkeley student was arrested on charges of felony vandalism and inciting a riot”.</p>	<p>Too much text:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 10px 0;"> <p>at least one student was arrested after a struggle between students and police, in which a glass door was broken in the rear of the building, university police said. A UC Berkeley student was arrested on charges of felony vandalism and inciting a riot, police added. (2709)</p> </div>
Article # 1021 - Detroit students rally on campus against Proposition 2	
Good	Not so good
<p>Included presence of the police and their actions:</p> <p>University Police officers arrived at the Diag following a report of a large crowd. (6192)</p> <p>Officers were present when students unexpectedly dispersed, (6192)</p> <p>police presence initially caused some of the students to disperse, the encouragement of other students kept the rally going. (6192)</p>	<p>Same coder also included declarations of an official, which is not needed:</p> <p>A UMPD official added that the group's presence was complicated by the fact that the organizations involved did not formally inform the University of their intent to demonstrate on the Diag, as many groups do. (6192)</p>

Property damage:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Just captures the damage done:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Property damage ^ +</p> <p style="text-align: center;">a glass door was bro ... rear of the building x</p> <p>Full description of property damage was cut off by interface (this is how it would look like when you code it too).</p>	<p>Second sentence is unnecessary because it was captured elsewhere:</p> <p>a glass door was broken in the rear of the building, university police said. A UC Berkeley student was arrested on charges of felony vandalism and inciting a riot, police added (2709)</p>

Related protests involving other universities

Article # 1522 - UCLA students protest tuition costs, other campus issues on May Day	
Good	Not so good
<p>Provided with more information about protests and locations:</p> <p>protested in solidarity with other May Day protests across University of California, California State University and community college campuses (5079)</p>	<p>Included information that is not needed (first paragraph):</p> <p>Many protesters wore red strips of cloth safety-pinned to their clothing. Mouzaoui said the red squares of cloth were used to give protesters a sense of unity and demonstrate their solidarity with protesters on other campuses. (5079)</p> <p>protested in solidarity with other May Day protests across University of California, California State University and community college campuses (5079)</p>
Article # 1533 - Aztecs walk out for May Day fee protest	
Good	Not so good
<p>Provided information about the location and the event:</p> <p>The protest was part of a larger effort by other California State Universities, University of California campuses and community colleges. Students collaborated to create events across campuses and protest the issues faced at their own schools. (7666)</p>	<p>Did not include information (where available) on how the protests were related:</p> <p>The protest was part of a larger effort by other California State Universities, University of California campuses and community colleges.</p>

Part of protest occurs off-campus

Article #1263 - Columbia students arrested in DC as part of XL Dissent protest against Keystone XL pipeline	
Good	Not so good
<p>Indicates the off-campus geographic location(s), i.e. where they are and some text indicating what they did off-campus.</p> <p>The XL Dissent protest started Sunday morning with a rally in Georgetown University's Red Square, after which students marched for two miles through the streets of Washington to the White House. Protesters laid out black tarps representing oil spills along the way, including one in front of Secretary of State John Kerry's house. The march ended with a rally in front of the White House and a demonstration in which students zip-tied themselves to the White House fence or pretended to die on top of an "oil spill." (6589)</p>	<p>Provided information isn't enough:</p> <p>students marched for two miles through the streets of Washington to the White House. (6462)</p>
Article #5198 - Knox students take back the night from violence	
Good	Not so good
<p>Indicates the off-campus geographic location:</p> <p>"From Old Main, the group proceeded to go down Cherry Street into downtown Galesburg. Onlookers seemed puzzled as they attempted to figure out what the students were marching for. From downtown, through the public square, the group marched to the grassy quad in the middle of the apartments"</p>	<p>Provided information isn't enough:</p> <p>"the group proceeded to go down Cherry Street into downtown Galesburg."</p>

Size:

Article #235 - Badgers Against Racism rally protests 'Cinco de Mifflin' theme	
Good	Not so good
Provided full information of who is part of the crowd: A crowd of students, faculty and community members (2761)	Didn't provide information on who is part of the crowd or who else is present: crowd (2837) crowd of students, (2727)
Article # 2033 - Students, community members rally against police brutality	
Good	Not so good
Provided full information of who is part of the crowd: About 50 UC Berkeley students and community members (5155)	Didn't provide information on who is part of the crowd or who else is present: About 50

Target:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
	<p>University isn't target, just regents:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;"> <p>University of California Regents committee (2709)</p> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;"> <p>UC San Francisco (2709)</p> </div>
Article #235 - Badgers Against Racism rally protests 'Cinco de Mifflin' theme	
Good	Not so good
<p>Included the group that provoked the issue:</p> <p>Mifflin Street Block Party (2924)</p>	<p>Didn't select the group the protesters were opposing and included the university and the community:</p> <p>University of Wisconsin - Madison (2924)</p> <p>UW community (2727)</p>

University names:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Captured the universities mentioned in the article which is not the university where the newspaper is from:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">University names ^ +</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">UC Berkeley ✕UC San Francisco ✕	<p>UC is a system, not a university name. Only capture other universities, exclude the university where the newspaper was from:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;"><p>UC (2546)</p></div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; padding: 5px;"><p>UCLA (2546)</p></div>

University officials:

Article #2211 - UC Regents committee approves five-year tuition increase plan despite protests	
Good	Not so good
<p>Included names and titles:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">University officials ^ +</p> <hr/> <p>University of Califo ... ia Regents committee ✕</p> <p>UC President Janet Napolitano ✕</p> <p>Nathan Brosom, the U ... of financial officer ✕</p> <p>Regent Sherry Lansing ✕</p> <p>Full name and title was cut off by interface (this is how it would look like when you code it too).</p>	<p>Missed titles and some other officials:</p> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;">Janet Napolitano (2573)</div> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; padding: 5px; margin: 5px 0;">Regent Sherry Lansing. (2573)</div>
Article # 98 - Eighteen Occupy Cal protesters detained Friday morning	
Good	Not so good
<p>Included names and titles:</p> <p>Claire Holmes, campus associate vice chancellor for public affairs. (3979)</p> <p>Executive Vice Chancellor and Provost George Breslauer (3979)</p> <p>Vice Chancellor for Administration and Finance John Wilton (3979)</p>	<p>Missing titles:</p> <p>Claire Holmes. (3979)</p> <p>George Breslauer (3979)</p> <p>John Wilton (3979)</p>

University responses:

Article # 122 - UC Santa Cruz, UC San Diego protests include traffic blockages, occupations	
Good	Not so good
<p>Captured the names of the actors, their titles and what they said:</p> <p>In an email to students, UC Santa Cruz Chancellor George Blumenthal shared similar concerns. "We wholeheartedly support advocacy in support of education," he said in the email. "However, we take issue with a protest that simultaneously denies students access to those classes for which they have paid." (3808)</p> <p>Campus spokesperson Jeff Gattas said the presence of police officers in plain clothes at protests was not unusual. "We always have plainclothes officers at all gatherings," he said. "It's our protocol." (3810)</p>	<p>Provided similar information, but the quotes are separated from actors, so it is difficult to identify who said them:</p> <p>In an email to students, UC Santa Cruz Chancellor George Blumenthal shared similar concerns. (3986)</p> <p>"We wholeheartedly support advocacy in support of education," he said in the email. "However, we take issue with a protest that simultaneously denies students access to those classes for which they have paid3." (3986)</p> <p>Campus spokesperson Jeff Gattas said the presence of police officers in plain clothes at protests was not unusual. (3987)</p> <p>"We always have plainclothes officers at all gatherings," he said. "It's our protocol." (3987)</p>
Article # 244 - Police block entrances to Albany farm encampment	
Good	Not so good
<p>Provided detailed information about actors, titles, responses and quotes:</p> <p>UC Berkeley spokesperson Dan Mogulof said Wednesday morning that pedestrians were free to come and go as they pleased from the tract even after police blockaded the entrances</p>	<p>Information registered is similar. However, there are some issues about what is selected, such as the first sentence about police responses and missing who "issued several open letters" (third sentence):</p> <p>pedestrians were free to come and go as they pleased from the tract even after police</p>

<p>(3825)</p> <p>"Chemical agents are part of our admonishments," said UCPD spokesperson Lt. Eric Tejada. "If you assault the police or interfere at any time, that would be a possibility." (3825)</p> <p>The proposal - issued by Executive Vice Chancellor and Provost George Breslauer and Vice Chancellor of Administration and Finance John Wilton - asks that the protesters voluntarily dismantle the encampment and restore control of the land to the university. In return, water supply to the Gill Tract would be restored and negotiations with the campus could begin. (3825)</p> <p>"The offer is still on the table ... but we are taking steps necessary for the UC to regain control of its property," Mogulof said of Wednesday's UCPD action. (3825)</p> <p>Breslauer and Wilton have issued several open letters to the protesters over the past two weeks informing them that negotiations cannot begin until the encampment is disbanded and that legal action may be taken against them if they choose to stay. "We would still really like to see a peaceful resolution, but as we have said we are at the point where we need to evaluate other options in order to let research go forward," Mogulof said. Later in the day, a press release from Mogulof announced the UC had filed a lawsuit in Alameda County Superior Court on Wednesday against 14 individuals allegedly connected to the encampment. In the suit, the university "alleges that the defendants ... conspired to cut locks, enter the property illegally and establish an illegal encampment."</p>	<p>blockaded the entrances. (4237)</p> <p>The proposal - issued by Executive Vice Chancellor and Provost George Breslauer and Vice Chancellor of Administration and Finance John Wilton - asks that the protesters voluntarily dismantle the encampment and restore control of the land to the university. In return, water supply to the Gill Tract would be restored and negotiations with the campus could begin. (4237)</p> <p>issued several open letters to the protesters over the past two weeks informing them that negotiations cannot begin until the encampment is disbanded and that legal action may be taken against them if they choose to stay. (4237)</p> <p>Later in the day, a press release from Mogulof announced the UC had filed a lawsuit in Alameda County Superior Court on Wednesday against 14 individuals allegedly connected to the encampment. In the suit, the university "alleges that the defendants ... conspired to cut locks, enter the property illegally and establish an illegal encampment." (4237)</p>
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(3825)	
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Violence/attack against persons by protesters:

Example	
Good	Not so good
<p>Gives description of protesters engaging in physical violence</p> <p>“On Friday afternoon, a counter-protester was punched by a pro-gun activist during a heated 2nd amendment protest at UT Austin.”</p>	<p>Does not provide enough information:</p> <p>“On Friday afternoon, a counter-protester was punched.”</p>

Violence/attack against protestors by bystanders

<p>#12677: UPDATED: Police investigate alleged assault against anti-choice protestor at Ryerson</p>	
<p>Good</p>	<p>Not so good</p>
<p>Included all actions of violence done by protesters against individuals or a group:</p> <p>“Gabby Skwarko, a Ryerson student and member of Ryerson Reproductive Justice Collective (RRJC), shoved anti-choise protestors at the Gould and Victoria streets intersection”</p> <p>“Skwarko kicked the graphic anti-choice sign Alleyne was holding. She then picked up a small cart and clamp that were on the ground in the middle of the circle of TAA protestors, threw the items at them and started to grab and push Somers. The footage shows that Skwarko then reached into Somers’ backpack, pulled out a metal water bottle and smashed it on the ground. She continued to shove Somers until other people stepped in and separated the two.”</p>	<p>Included too much information (red text):</p> <p>“Gabby Skwarko, a Ryerson student and member of Ryerson Reproductive Justice Collective (RRJC), shoved anti-choise protestors at the Gould and Victoria streets intersection”</p> <p>“Skwarko kicked the graphic anti-choice sign Alleyne was holding. She then picked up a small cart and clamp that were on the ground in the middle of the circle of TAA protestors, threw the items at them and started to grab and push Somers. The footage shows that Skwarko then reached into Somers’ backpack, pulled out a metal water bottle and smashed it on the ground. She continued to shove Somers until other people stepped in and separated the two.”</p> <p>“The police and paramedics were called to the scene and Somers was taken to hospital with non-life threatening injuries. She said paramedics were called because she was limping, her wrist was sore and swollen and her right leg had deep bruising.”</p>

Tab 4: Preset

<p style="text-align: center;">Forms</p> <p style="text-align: center;">[Click here to go back to section]</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Issues</p> <p style="text-align: center;">[Click here to go back to section]</p>
<p>Selecting more than one option is appropriate when applicable:</p> <hr/> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Form</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Blockade/slowdown/disruption <input type="checkbox"/> Boycott <input type="checkbox"/> Civil disobedience <input type="checkbox"/> Hunger Strike <input type="checkbox"/> Information distribution/leafleting <input type="checkbox"/> March <input type="checkbox"/> Occupation/sit-in <input type="checkbox"/> Petition <input type="checkbox"/> Picketing <input type="checkbox"/> Press conference <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Property damage <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Rally/demonstration <input type="checkbox"/> Riot <input type="checkbox"/> Strike/walkout/lockout <input type="checkbox"/> Symbolic display/symbolic action <input type="checkbox"/> Vigil <input type="checkbox"/> Violence/attack <input type="checkbox"/> _Other Form 	<p>Selecting more than one option is appropriate when applicable:</p> <hr/> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Issue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Abortion (Against)/Pro-life <input type="checkbox"/> Abortion (For) <input type="checkbox"/> Accessibility <input type="checkbox"/> Animal rights <input type="checkbox"/> Anti-colonial/political independence <input type="checkbox"/> Anti-war/peace <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic foreign policy <input type="checkbox"/> Economy/inequality <input type="checkbox"/> Environmental <input type="checkbox"/> Faith-based discrimination <input type="checkbox"/> Feminism/women's issues <input type="checkbox"/> Free speech <input type="checkbox"/> Gun control <input type="checkbox"/> Gun owner rights <input type="checkbox"/> Human and civil rights <input type="checkbox"/> LGB+/Sexual orientation <input type="checkbox"/> Labor and work <input type="checkbox"/> Men's rights <input type="checkbox"/> Police violence/anti-law enforcement <input type="checkbox"/> Political corruption/malfeasance <input type="checkbox"/> Pro-law enforcement <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual assault/violence <input type="checkbox"/> Social services and welfare <input type="checkbox"/> Traditional marriage/family <input type="checkbox"/> Transgender issues <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tuition, fees, financial aid <input type="checkbox"/> University governance, policies, programs, admin <input type="checkbox"/> _Not relevant <input type="checkbox"/> _Other Issue

<p style="text-align: center;">Racial issues</p> <p style="text-align: center;">[Click here to go back to section]</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Target</p> <p style="text-align: center;">[Click here to go back to section]</p>
<p>Not relevant is chosen when the event doesn't seem to be related to racial issues:</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Racial Issue</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Affirmative action (Against) <input type="checkbox"/> Affirmative action (For) <input type="checkbox"/> All Lives Matter <input type="checkbox"/> Anti-racism <input type="checkbox"/> Campus climate <input type="checkbox"/> Cultural appropriation <input type="checkbox"/> Curriculum, programming, support services, policies <input type="checkbox"/> Hate crimes/Anti-minority violence <input type="checkbox"/> Hate speech <input type="checkbox"/> Immigration (Against) <input type="checkbox"/> Immigration (For) <input type="checkbox"/> Indigenous issues <input type="checkbox"/> K-12 education <input type="checkbox"/> Memorials & anniversaries <input type="checkbox"/> Police violence <input type="checkbox"/> Prison/mass incarceration <input type="checkbox"/> Pro-police <input type="checkbox"/> Racial/ethnic pride - minority <input type="checkbox"/> Racial/ethnic pride - white <input type="checkbox"/> Racist/racialized symbols <input type="checkbox"/> Reconciliation <input type="checkbox"/> Reparations <input type="checkbox"/> Sovereignty/governance <input type="checkbox"/> Underrepresentation in hiring <input type="checkbox"/> White supremacy (Against) <input type="checkbox"/> White supremacy (For) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> _Not relevant <input type="checkbox"/> _Other Issue 	<p>Selecting more than one option is appropriate when applicable:</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Target</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Domestic government <input type="checkbox"/> Ethnic/racial group <input type="checkbox"/> Foreign government <input type="checkbox"/> Individual <input type="checkbox"/> Intergovernmental organization <input type="checkbox"/> Medical facility/organization <input type="checkbox"/> Non-governmental organization <input type="checkbox"/> Other minority group <input type="checkbox"/> Political party <input type="checkbox"/> Private/business <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> University/school <input type="checkbox"/> _Other target